

World News of Natural Sciences

An International Scientific Journal

WNOFNS 29(2) (2020) 75-150

EISSN 2543-5426

World Inventory of Beetles of the Family *Chrysomelidae* (Coleoptera). Part 2: Eastern Europe and Northern Asia. Check List from 1768 to 2004

Tomasz Borowski

The II Laboratory of Research Works,
The Independent Institution of Biopaleogeography and Biophysics,
22 Mickiewicza Str., Złocieniec, Poland

E-mail address: tomasz.elvis.borowski@wp.pl

ABSTRACT

This paper presents list of beetles of the family *Chrysomelidae* and their occurrence. The paper includes: 8 subfamilies, 10 tribes, 7 subtribes, 74 genera, 77 subgenera and 933 species of beetles belonging to the family *Chrysomelidae*.

Keywords: *Chrysomelidae*, *Chrysomelinae*, *Cryptocephalinae*, *Galerucinae*, *Lamprosomatinae*, *Orsodacninae*, *Megalopodinae*, *Synetinae*, *Zeugophorinae*

Subfamilies

<i>Chrysomelinae</i>76
<i>Cryptocephalinae</i>109
<i>Galerucinae</i>134
<i>Lamprosomatinae</i>146
<i>Orsodacninae</i>147
<i>Megalopodinae</i>147
<i>Synetinae</i>147
<i>Zeugophorinae</i>148

– Check List –

(Continuation of the Part 1)

Subfamily *Chrysomelinae* Latreille, 1802

Tribe *Timarchini* Motschulsky, 1860

Genus *Timarcha* Dejean, 1821

Subgenus *Timarcha (Metallochimarcha)* Motschulsky, 1860

Timarcha (Metallochimarcha) hummeli hummeli Faldermann, 1837

Distribution: N Caucasus, W Transcaucasia

Timarcha (Metallochimarcha) hummeli armeniaca Faldermann, 1837

Distribution: Armenia

Timarcha (Metallochimarcha) metallica (Laicharting, 1781)

Distribution: Mountains of SW and Central Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians

Subgenus *Timarcha (Timarcha)* Dejean, 1821

Timarcha (Timarcha) goettingensis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North

Timarcha (Timarcha) rugulosa Herrich-Schaffer, 1838

Distribution: SE Europe, Moldavia, Ukraine, Crimea

Timarcha (Timarcha) tenebricosa tenebricosa (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution: W and S Europe, Steppe zone of Ukraine and European Russia

Timarcha (Timarcha) tenebricosa iberica Motschulsky, 1849

Distribution: Caucasus

Timarcha (Timarcha) tenebricosa motschulskyi Bechyne, 1945

Distribution: Crimea

Tribe *Chrysomelini* Latreille, 1802

Subtribus *Chrysolinina* Chen, 1936

Genus *Ambrostoma* Motschulsky, 1860

Ambrostoma quadriimpressum Motschulsky, 1845

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, N China, Korea

Genus *Crosita* Motschulsky, 1860

Crosita afghanica Lopatin, 1962

Distribution: E Tajikistan (Badakhshan), NE Afghanistan

Crosita altaica altaica (Gebler, 1823)

Distribution: Central and E Kazakhstan, Tarbagatay, Central Tian-Shan, S Asian Russia (Altai), Mongolia

Crosita altaica feldermanni (Krynicky, 1832)

Distribution: SE European Russia, Central and E Kazakhstan (Dry Steppe), Mongolia

Crosita maximovitschi (Zubkov, 1833)

Distribution: NE and Central Kazakhstan (Saur Mountain Range), SW Mongolia

Crosita bogutensis Lopatin, 1996

Distribution: Kazakhstan (Boguty Mountains)

Crosita elegans Lopatin, 1968

Distribution: Mongolia

Crosita heptapotamica Jacobson, 1895

Distribution: Central Tian-Shan

Crosita kowalewskii (Gebler, 1836)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Altai), Mongolia, NW China

Crosita longipes Jacobson, 1898

Distribution: Asia Russia (S Altai, Tuva), Mongolia

Crosita pigra J. Weise, 1894

Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva), Mongolia

Genus *Gnathomela* Jacobson, 1895

Gnathomela glasunovi Bechyne, 1962

Distribution: Uzbekistan (Nuratau Mountain Range)

Gnathomela laevigata laevigata Lopatin, 1972

Distribution: Uzbekistan (Kuramin Mountain Range)

Gnathomela laevigata kirghizica Lopatin, 1990

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan, (Kyrgyz Alatau Mountain Range)

Gnathomela meridionalis Lopatin, 1972

Distribution: S Uzbekistan (Baisuntau Mountsin Range)

Gnathomela mutica Lopatin, 1972

Distribution: W Tian-Shan (Ugam, Pskem and Karzhantau Mountain Ranges)

Gnathomela ovczinnikovi Lopatin, 1990

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Fergan Mountain Range)

Gnathomela praestans Lopatin, 1972

Distribution: W Tian-Shan

Gnathomela valida valida Lopatin, 1972

Distribution: W Tian-Shan

Gnathomela valida nuratavica Lopatin, 1972

Distribution: Uzbekistan (Nuratau Mountain Range)

Genus *Chrysolina* Motschulsky, 1860

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Bittotaenia)* Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysolina (Bittotaenia) grata grata (Faldermann, 1837)

Distribution: Transcaucasia, SW Turkmenistan, N Iran

Chrysolina (Bittotaenia) grata turanica (Reitter, 1888)

Distribution: SW Turkmenistan, SW Tajikistan

Chrysolina (Bittotaenia) salviae salviae (Germar, 1824)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Syria

Chrysolina (Bittotaenia) salviae sculptipennis (Faldermann, 1937)

Distribution: Caucasus, Turkey

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Pseudocrosita)*** Lopatin, 1999

Chrysolina (Pseudocrosita) bactriana Lopatin, 1961

Distribution: S Tajikistan (low mountains), S Kyrgyzstan (Alai Mountain Range)

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Lithopteroides)*** E. Strand, 1935

Chrysolina (Lithopteroides) exanthematica exanthematica (Wiedemann, 1821)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East), China, N India, Vietnam

Chrysolina (Lithopteroides) exanthematica gemmifera Motschulsky, 1860

Distribution: S Siberia, Mongolia

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Crositops)*** Marseul, 1883

Chrysolina (Crositops) kabaki Lopatin, 1988,

Distribution: E Kazakhstan (High Mountains)

Chrysolina (Crositops) pedestris (Gebler, 1823)

Distribution: E Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Altai)

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Timarchoptera)*** Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysolina (Timarchoptera) haemochlora (Gebler, 1823)

Distribution: W Siberia, Mongolia

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Chrysocrosita)*** Bechyne, 1950

Chrysolina (Chrysocrosita) jakovlevi (J. Weise, 1894)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva, Sayan)

Chrysolina (Chrysocrosita) spectabilis spectabilis Motschulsky, 1860

Distribution: NE Asian Russia (Kamchatka)

Chrysolina (Chrysocrosita) polychroma L. Medvedev, 1975

Distribution: Asian Russia (Sayan), N Mongolia

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Lithocrosita)*** L. Medvedev, 1982

Chrysolina (Lithocrosita) rugulosa (Gebler, 1841)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai)

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Heliostola)* Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysolina (Heliostola) carpathica (Fuss, 1856)

Distribution: SE Europe, W Ukraine (Carpathians)

Chrysolina (Heliostola) katonica Lopatin, 1988

Distribution: E Kazakhstan

Chrysolina (Heliostola) lichenis (Richter, 1820)

Distribution: Central and SE Europe, W Ukraine

Chrysolina (Heliostola) montana (Gebler, 1847)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai)

Chrysolina (Heliostola) schewyrevi (Jacobson, 1895)

Distribution: Asian Russia (W Siberia, Altai, Transbaikalia)

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Paraheliostola)* L. Medvedev, 1992

Chrysolina (Paraheliostola) lomakini Mikailov, 2002

Distribution: Asian Russia (Khakassia)

Chrysolina (Paraheliostola) soiota soiota (Jacobson, 1924)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Sayan)

Chrysolina (Paraheliostola) soiota khakassa Mikhailov, 2002

Distribution: Asian Russia (Khakassia)

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Pleurosticha)* Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysolina (Pleurosticha) cavigera (J. Sahlberg, 1885)

Distribution: Arctic, N Siberia

Chrysolina (Pleurosticha) gebleri gebleri L. Medvedev, 1992

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai)

Chrysolina (Pleurosticha) gebleri sajanensis L. Medvedev, 1979

Distribution: Asian Russia (Cisbaikalia, Transbaikalia), Mongolia

Chrysolina (Pleurosticha) latimargo (J. Weise, 1896)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Siberia), Mongolia

Chrysolina (Pleurosticha) subcostata (Gebler, 1848)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East), N Japan

Chrysolina (Pleurosticha) sylvatica (Gebler, 1823)
Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai)

Chrysolina (Pleurosticha) tolli (Jacobson, 1910)
Distribution: Arctic Asia

Chrysolina (Pleurosticha) uraltuvensis Mikhailov, 2000
Asian Russia (W Sayan, S of Krasnoyarsk Prov.)

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Arctolina)* Kontkanen, 1959

Chrysolina (Arctolina) ballioni (Lopatin, 1968)
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan

Chrysolina (Arctolina) boeberi (Harold, 1874)
Distribution: Asian Russia (Chukotka, Magadan Distr., Kamchatka), Alaska

Chrysolina (Arctolina) bungei (Jacobson, 1910)
Distribution: NE Siberia

Chrysolina (Arctolina) cyanella (Gebler, 1830)
Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai)

Chrysolina (Arctolina) dolini Lopatin, 1999
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan (Dzhungar Alatau)

Chrysolina (Arctolina) dubeshkoe (L. Medvedev, 1974)
Distribution: Mongolia

Chrysolina (Arctolina) kaikana Lopatin, 1992
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan (Kikan Mountain Range)

Chrysolina (Arctolina) kryzhanovskyi (Lopatin, 1968)
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan

Chrysolina (Arctolina) octocosta (Jacobson, 1924)
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan (Dzhungar Alatau)

Chrysolina (Arctolina) oirota Lopatin, 1990
Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai)

Chrysolina (Arctolina) saurica (Jacobson, 1924)
Distribution: E Kazakhstan

Chrysolina (Arctolina) septentrionalis (Menetries, 1851)
Distribution: N part of European Russia, Asian Russia (Krasnoyarsk Prov., Transbaikalia)

Chrysolina (Arctolina) subsulcata (Mannerheim, 1853)

Distribution: Arctic Asia, Alaska

Chrysolina (Arctolina) tastavica Lopatin, 1992

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan (Tastau Mountain Range)

Chrysolina (Arctolina) teleutica (Jacobson, 1924)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai)

Chrysolina (Arctolina) valichanovi Lopatin, 1990

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan (Dzhungar Alatau)

Chrysolina (Arctolina) wolosowiczi (Jacobson, 1910)

Distribution: NE Asian Russia (Novosiberian Is.)

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Sibiriella)*** L. Medvedev, 1999

Chrysolina (Sybiriella) paradoxa L. Medvedev, 1999

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, Sayan)

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Altailina)*** Mikhailov, 2000

Chrysolina (Altailina) capricornis Mikhailov, 2000

Distribution: Asian Russia (W Sayan)

Chrysolina (Altailina) dudkoi dudkoi Mikhailov, 2000

Distribution: Asian Russia (W Sayan)

Chrysolina (Altailina) dudkoi ivanovskiana Mikhailov, 2000

Distribution: Asian Russia (W Sayan)

Chrysolina (Altailina) kholsunica Mikhailov, 2000

Distribution: Asian Russia (W Sayan)

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Pezocrosita)*** Jacobson, 1901

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) almaatica (Lopatin, 1962)

Distribution: S Kazakhstan

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) brevilata (Heyden, 1886)

Distribution: Mountains of Kyrgyzstan and S Kazakhstan

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) brunnicornis brunnicornis (J. Weise, 1887)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva), W Mongolia

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) brunicornis bermani (L. Medvedev, 1978)
Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Yakutia)

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) brunicornis vrangeliana Voronova, 1982
Distribution: NE Asian Russia (Wrangel Is.)

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) convexcollis (Jacobson, 1901)
Asian Russia (Tuva), Mongolia

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) discriminata (Jacobson, 1901)
Distribution: Asian Russia (E Siberia), Mongolia

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) erzinica Mikhailov, 2002
Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva)

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) glebi Lopatin, 1988
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) helenae (Lopatin, 1968)
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) hyperboreica Mikhailov, 2002
Distribution: Arctic Asia (Polar Urals)

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) juldusana (Lopatin, 1962)
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, NW China

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) ketmenica (Lopatin, 1970)
Distribution: E Kazakhstan (Ketmen Mountain Range)

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) kiritschenkoi (Lopatin, 1970)
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) koenigi (Jacobson, 1895)
Distribution: Mountains of Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) lehri (Lopatin, 1970)
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) lopatini (Mohr, 1966)
Distribution: Asian Russia (Cisbaikalia, Transbaikalia), N Mongolia

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) medvedevi (Lopatin, 1970)
Distribution: E Kazakhstan

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) mohri (Lopatin, 1970)
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan

- Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) mongolensis* (Lopatin, 1966)
Distribution: Mongolia
- Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) obovata* (Jacobson, 1895)
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Central Tian-Shan)
- Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) ordinata* (Gebler, 1823)
Distribution: E Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (SW Siberia, Altais)
- Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) oshanini* (Lopatin, 1965)
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan
- Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) petrenkoi* Lopatin, 1992
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan (Dzhungar Alatau)
- Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) pusa* (Lopatin, 1962)
Distribution: Asian Russia (Buryatia), Mongolia
- Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) rufilabris* (Faldermann, 1835)
Distribution: Asian Russia (E Siberia), Mongolia
- Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) sahlbergiana* (Jacobson, 1901)
Distribution: Asian Russia (Sayan), N Mongolia
- Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) sajanica* (Jacobson, 1925)
Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva)
- Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) sarcandica* Lopatin, 1990
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan
- Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) sogdiorum* (J. Weise, 1892)
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan
- Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) tibialis* (Jacobson, 1895)
Distribution: Asian Russia (Sayan, Tuva)
- Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) tschatkalica* (Lopatin, 1970)
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan
- Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) tuvensis* L. Medvedev, 1976
Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva)
- Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) ulughchemica* Mikhailov, 2002
Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva)
- Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) undulata undulata* (Gebler, 1834)
Distribution: S Siberia

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) undulata asperata Lopatin, 1990

Distribution: E Kazakhstan

Chrysolina (Pezocrosita) urjanchaica (Jacobson, 1925)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva)

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Stichoptera)*** Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysolina (Stichoptera) gypsophilae (Kuster, 1845)

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North, Caucasus, Turkey, NW and Central Kazakhstan

Chrysolina (Stichoptera) kuesteri (Helliesen, 1912)

Distribution: S and Central Europe

Chrysolina (Stichoptera) pavlenkoi (Jacobson, 1924)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.)

Chrysolina (Stichoptera) sanguinolenta (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: S, Central, and E Europe, Kazakhstan (Steppe zone), Asian Russia (S Siberia, Russian Far East), Mongolia

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Craspeda)*** Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysolina (Craspeda) jennisiejensis (Breit, 1920)

Distribution: European Russia (Tambov Distr.). Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East), Mongolia

Chrysolina (Craspeda) limbata limbata (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution: Europe except for the North, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia east to Baikal)

Chrysolina (Craspeda) limbata discipennis (Faldermann, 1835)

Distribution: SE Europe, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Yakutia), Mongolia

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Taeniosticha)*** Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysolina (Taeniosticha) alatafica (Jacobson, 1910)

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan, NW China

Chrysolina (Taeniosticha) changaica (Lopatin, 1968)

Distribution: Mongolia

Chrysolina (Taeniosticha) imperfecta imperfecta Breit, 1920

Distribution: S Turkmenistan, Iran, N Afghanistan

Chrysolina (Taeniosticha) koktumensis Lopatin et Kulenova, 1987

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan (Dzhungar Alatau)

Chrysolina (Taeniosticha) kuldzhensis Lopatin, 1976

Distribution: E Tian-Shan

Chrysolina (Taeniosticha) reitteri reitteri (J. Weise, 1884)

Distribution: Steppe of European Russia and Ukraine, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Sayan)

Chrysolina (Taeniosticha) reitteri bakuensis Bechyne, 1952

Distribution: Azerbaijan

Chrysolina (Taeniosticha) reitteri pseudolurida (Roubal, 1936)

Distribution: W Caucasus, Turkey

Chrysolina (Taeniosticha) reitteri jailensis Bechyne, 1952

Distribution: S Crimea

Chrysolina (Taeniosticha) reitteri saxonica Silfverberg, 1977

Distribution: Central and western parts of E Europe

Chrysolina (Taeniosticha) tianshanica (Jacobson, 1910)

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan (Tian-Shan)

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Ovosoma)*** Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysolina (Ovosoma) susterai Bechyne, 1950

Distribution: SE and southern part of Europe, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Altai)

Chrysolina (Ovosoma) sahlbergi (Menetries, 1832)

Distribution: Caucasus, Turkey, Syria, Israel

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Chrysomorpha)*** Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysolina (Chrysomorpha) cerealis cerealis (Linnaeus, 1767)

Distribution: Europe, Kazakhstan

Chrysolina (Chrysomorpha) cerealis cyaneoaurata (Motschulsky, 1860)

Distribution: Siberia, Mongolia

Chrysolina (Chrysomorpha) cerealis rufolineata (Motschulsky, 1860)

Distribution: N Caucasus, Kazakhstan

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Colaphosoma)*** Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysolina (Colaphosoma) sturmi (Westhoff, 1882)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Siberia

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Colaphoptera)*** Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysolina (Colaphoptera) abchasica (J. Weise, 1892)

Distribution: W Caucasus

Chrysolina (Colaphoptera) adzharica Lopatin, 1988

Distribution: SW Georgia, N Turkey

Chrysolina (Colaphoptera) apsilaena Silfverberg, 1977

Distribution: Caucasus

Chrysolina (Colaphoptera) caspica (J. Weise, 1892)

Distribution: Caucasus

Chrysolina (Colaphoptera) marcasitica marcasitica (Germar, 1824)

Distribution: Mountains of Central Europe, W Ukraine (Carpathians)

Chrysolina (Colaphoptera) marcasitica turgida (J. Weise, 1882)

Distribution: Sudeten and Carpathians

Chrysolina (Colaphoptera) pliginskii (Reitter, 1913)

Distribution: Crimea

Chrysolina (Colaphoptera) porphyrea (Faldermann, 1837)

Distribution: Caucasus

Chrysolina (Colaphoptera) purpurascens (Germar, 1822)

Distribution: Central Europe, W Ukraine (Carpathians)

Chrysolina (Colaphoptera) rosti (J. Weise, 1892)

Distribution: W Caucasus

Chrysolina (Colaphoptera) rufa rufa (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: Mountains of Central Europe, Carpathians

Chrysolina (Colaphoptera) rufa lapidaria Bechyne, 1950

Distribution: Central Europe, W Moldavia

Chrysolina (Colaphoptera) trapezicollis Bechyne, 1952

Distribution: Caucasus

Chrysolina (Colaphoptera) umbratilis (J. Weise, 1887)

Distribution: Mountains of Central Europe, Carpathians

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Ovostoma)* Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysolina (Ovostoma) globipennis (Suffrian, 1851)

Distribution: Central and S Europe, Moldavia, Ukraine

Chrysolina (Ovostoma) olivieri (Bedel, 1892)

Distribution: Mountains of Central and S Europe, Ukraine

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Euchrysolina)* Bechyne, 1950

Chrysolina (Euchrysolina) graminis graminis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Tuva, Altai), Mongolia

Chrysolina (Euchrysolina) graminis artemisiae Motschulsky, 1860

Distribution: SE Europe, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, S Siberia

Chrysolina (Euchrysolina) graminis auraria Motschulsky, 1860

Distribution: Russian Far East, Japan

Chrysolina (Euchrysolina) virgata Motschulsky, 1860

Distribution: Russian Far East, Japan

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Erythrochysa)* Bechyne, 1950

Chrysolina (Erythrochysa) polita (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: All over Palaearctic

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Menthastriella)* Bechyne, 1950

Chrysolina (Menthastriella) herbacea herbacea (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North, Caucasus, Turkey, Transcaucasia, Middle East, W Kazakhstan, W Turkmenistan

Chrysolina (Menthastriella) coeruleans coeruleans (L. G. Scriba, 1791)

Distribution: Mountains of Central Europe, Karelia, Belarus

Chrysolina (Menthastrisella) coeruleans relicta L. Medvedev, 1977

Distribution: Urals

Chrysolina (Menthastrisella) coeruleans splendorifera Motschulsky, 1860

Distribution: Caucasus, Iran, Iraq

Chrysolina (Menthastrisella) coeruleans uzbekorum Berchyne, 1950

Distribution: Uzbekistan, Tajikistan

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Colaphodes)* Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysolina (Colaphodes) haemoptera haemoptera (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North, Turkey

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Hypericia)* Bedel, 1892

Chrysolina (Hypericia) cuprina cuprina (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North, Introduced to USA and Australia

Chrysolina (Hypericia) cuprina dilecta Bechyne, 1952

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, Sayan)

Chrysolina (Hypericia) didymata (L. G. Scriba, 1791)

Distribution: Europe, Turkey

Chrysolina (Hypericia) difficilis difficilis (Motschulsky, 1869)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, Sayan)

Chrysolina (Hypericia) difficilis ussuriensis (Jacobson, 1901)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), NE China

Chrysolina (Hypericia) difficilis yezoensis (Matsumura, 1911)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Sakhalin), Korea, Japan

Chrysolina (Hypericia) geminata (Paykull, 1799)

Distribution: S, Central and E Europe

Chrysolina (Hypericia) hyperici hyperici (Forster, 1771)

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan

Chrysolina (Hypericia) hyperici daghestanica (Reitter, 1912)

Distribution: E Caucasus (Daghestan)

Chrysolina (Hypericia) seriepunctata (J. Weise, 1887)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.)

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Allohypericia)* Bechyne, 1950

Chrysolina (Allohypericia) aeruginosa aeruginosa (Faldermann, 1835)

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Siberia, Mongolia

Chrysolina (Allohypericia) aeruginosa sibirica (J. Weise, 1887)

Distribution: Russian Far East

Chrysolina (Allohypericia) arctica L. Medvedev, 1980

Distribution: Asian Russia (Wrangel Is.)

Chrysolina (Allohypericia) koltzei koltzei (J. Weise, 1887)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Siberia, Amurland)

Chrysolina (Allohypericia) kotzei brunneipennis (Matsumura, 1911)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Sakhalin), Japan

Chrysolina (Allohypericia) perforata perforata (Gebler, 1830)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Siberia, Altai, Sayan), N and NW Mongolia

Chrysolina (Allohypericia) perforata pallidipes L. Medvedev, 1980

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Tuva), Mongolia

Chrysolina (Allohypericia) perforata simillima Mohr, 1966

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia), N Mongolia

Chrysolina (Allohypericia) purpurata Faldermann, 1833

Distribution: E Kazakhstan, S Siberia

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Anopachys)* Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysolina (Anopachys) aurichalcea aurichalcea (Mannerheim, 1825)

Distribution: Forest and Steppe zone of European Russia, Crimea, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Russian Far East), Mongolia, China, Korea, Japan

Chrysolina (Anopachys) aurichalcea bohémica G. Muller, 1949

Distribution: Central Europe, Ukraine

Chrysolina (Anopachys) lineella (J. Weise, 1887)

Distribution: Russian Far East

Chrysolina (Anopachys) lineigera (Jacobson, 1901)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Far East, Sakhalin), NE China, N Japan

Chrysolina (Anopachys) neglecta Bienkovsky, 1998

Distribution: Asian Russia (Khabarovsk Prov, Maritime Prov.)

Chrysolina (Anopachys) pala Bienkovsky, 1998

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.)

Chrysolina (Anopachys) quadrangulata (Motschulsky, 1860)

Distribution: Asian Russia (E Siberia, Russia Far East), N and Central Mongolia

Chrysolina (Anopachys) relucens (Rosenhauer, 1847)

Distribution: Central Europe (Alps), Coasts of White Sea, Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East)

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Caudatochrysa)*** Bechyne, 1950

Chrysolina (Caudatochrysa) aino Takizawa, 1970

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Kurile Is., Kunashir)

Chrysolina (Caudatochrysa) angusticollis Motschulsky, 1860

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, S Kurile Is.), N China, Japan

Chrysolina (Caudatochrysa) cyanopurpurea (Ballion, 1878)

Distribution: NW China, possible for SE Kazakhstan

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Chrysolina)*** Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysolina (Chrysolina) staphylaea staphylaea (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: All over the Holarctic

Chrysolina (Chrysolina) staphylaea daurica (Gebler, 1832)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Siberia, Maritime Prov.), Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, N China

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Minckia)*** E. Strand, 1935

Chrysolina (Minckia) chalcites (Germar, 1824)

Distribution: Europe, Central and S European Russia, S Ukraine, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near East, Turkmenistan, Tajikistan

Chrysolina (Minckia) oricalcia (O. F. Muller, 1776)

Distribution: Europe

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Vittatochrysa)*** Lopatin, 1977

Chrysolina (Vittatochrysa) nigrovittata (Ballion, 1878)

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, NW China

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Sphaeromela)* Bedel, 1892

Chrysolina (Sphaeromela) varians (Schaller, 1783)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asian Russia (W Siberia, Altais)

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Bechynea)* L. Medvedev, 1970

Chrysolina (Bechynea) nikolskii (Jacobson, 1899)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), Japan

Chrysolina (Bechynea) sulcicollis adzhalamica L. Medvedev, 1970

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Khabarovsk Prov.)

Chrysolina (Bechynea) sulcicollis sutschanica L. Medvedev, 1970

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.)

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Paracrosita)* Daccordi, 1982

Chrysolina (Paracrosita) armeniaca (Feldermann, 1837)

Distribution: Caucasus, S Turkmenistan

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Chalcoidea)* Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) analis (Linnaeus, 1767)

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North and South

Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) bodemeyeri (J. Weise, 1910)

Distribution: Turkmenistan (Kopetdagh Mountain Range), Iran

Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) carnifex (Fabricius, 1792)

Distribution: Europe, Ukraine, S European Russia, N and E Kazakhstan

Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) cinctipennis (Harold, 1874)

Distribution: Hungary, Ukraine, European Russia (Steppe and semi-desert zone), Kazakhstan (except for S and E)

Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) circumducta (Menetries, 1835)

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, NW China

Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) elbursica Lopatin, 1981

Distribution: S Turkmenistan, N Iran

Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) hyrcana (J. Weise, 1884)

Distribution: Daghestan, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan (except for the South)

***Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) instabilis* Maklin, 1877**

Distribution: Asian Russia (N of Middle and Northeastern Siberia, from Yenisei River in the west, up to Kolyma River in the east, Yakutia, Irkutsk Distr.)

***Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) levi* Ochrimenko, 1990**

Distribution: N Caucasus

***Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) lia* (Jacobson, 1895)**

Distribution: Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, S Kyrgyzstan, Iran, Afghanistan

***Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) marginata marginata* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Distribution: All over the Holarctic

***Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) marginata roubali* Bechyne, 1950**

Distribution: N Caucasus

***Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) marginata songorica* (Gebler, 1843)**

Distribution: SE and E Kazakhstan

***Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) marginata unificans* Bechyne, 1950**

Distribution: Transcaucasia, E Turkey

***Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) tesari* (Roubal, 1936)**

Distribution: Caucasus

***Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) turgaica* (Jacobson, 1910)**

Distribution: W Kazakhstan

***Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) unicolor unicolor* (Gebler, 1845)**

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan (N and Central Tian-Shan)

***Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) unicolor alaiensis* Lopatin, 1998**

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Alai Mountain Range)

***Chrysolina (Chalcoidea) zamotajlovi* L. Medvedev et Ochrimenko, 1991**

Distribution: Caucasus

Subgenus ***Chrysolina (Diachalcoidea)*** Bechyne, 1955

***Chrysolina (Diachalcoidea) sacarum sacarum* (J. Weise, 1890)**

Distribution: S and SE Kazakhstan, Central Asia (except for the Turkmenistan Deserts and Pamirs), Afghanistan

***Chrysolina (Diachalcoidea) sacarum embiense* Lopatin, 1996**

Distribution: W Kazakhstan

Subgenus *Chrysolina (Fastuolina)* Warchałowski, 1991

Chrysolina (Fastuolina) fastuosa (Scopoli, 1763)

Distribution: Europe, Asian Russia (W Siberia, Altai)

Genus *Oreina* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Subgenus *Oreina* (Allorina) J. Weise, 1902

Oreina (Allorina) bidentata Bontems, 1981

Distribution: Mountains of S Europe, Carpathians

Oreina (Allorina) coerulea coerulea (Olivier, 1790)

Distribution: Mountains of Central and SE Europe, Carpathians, W Belarus, S Ukraine from Carpathians in the west up to Dnepr River in the east, European Russia (except from N)

Oreina (Allorina) coerulea onega Bechyne, 1958

Distribution: Karelia

Oreina (Allorina) coerulea rareua Bechyne, 1958

Distribution: Bukowina

Subgenus *Oreina (Romalorina)* J. Weise, 1906

Oreina (Romalorina) alpestris (Schummel, 1843)

Distribution: Mountains of S, Central and E Europe, from Pyrenees to Carpathians

Oreina (Romalorina) basilea (Gebler, 1823)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, Tuva, Sayan, Transbaikalia), Mongolia

Oreina (Romalorina) bifrons (Fabricius, 1792)

Distribution: Mountains of Central and S Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians

Oreina (Romalorina) redikortzevi (Jacobson, 1925)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Sayan)

Oreina (Romalorina) viridis (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: Mountains of Central and S Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians

Subgenus *Oreina (Intricatorina)* Kuhnelt, 1984

Oreina (Intricatorina) intricata (Germar, 1824)

Distribution: Mountains of Central and S Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians

Oreina (Intricatorina) virgulata (Germar, 1824)

Distributions: Mountains of Central, S and SE Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians and Ciscarpathia

Subgenus ***Oreina (Oreina)*** Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Oreina (Oreina) cacaliae (Schrank, 1785)

Distribution: Mountains of Central and S Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians

Oreina (Oreina) speciosissima (Scopoli, 1763)

Distribution: Mountains of Central and S Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians

Genus ***Cecchiniola*** Jacobson, 1908

Cecchiniola platyscelidina Jacobson, 1898)

Distribution: Crimea

Genus ***Colaphellus*** J. Weise, 1916

Colaphellus alpinus alpinus (Gebler, 1834)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S and Middle Siberia), Mongolia

Colaphellus alpinus bowringii (Baly, 1865)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Far East), E Asia

Colaphellus apicalis (Menetries, 1849)

Distribution: Middle East, Central Asia (Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Kazakhstan)

Colaphellus sophiae sophiae (Schaller, 1783)

Distribution: Central Europe, W and S Ukraine, Central part of Russian Plain, Armenia

Colaphellus sophiae hoefti (Menetries, 1832)

Distribution: S and E Ukraine, Crimea, southern parts of European Russia, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, W Siberia

Genus ***Gastrophysa*** Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Subgenus ***Gastrophysa (Gastrophysa)*** Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Gastrophysa (Gastrophysa) atrocyanea Motschulsky, 1860

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov., Sakhalin), Korea, China, Japan, Vietnam

Gastrophysa (Gastrophysa) mannerheimi (Stal, 1858)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Siberia, Amurland), Mongolia, N China

Gastrophysa (Gastrophysa) polygona (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe, Turkey, Central Asia, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Amurland), N China, Korea, N America

Gastrophysa (Gastrophysa) viridula viridula (DeGeer, 1775)

Distribution: Europe, SE Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W and Middle Siberia), N America

Gastrophysa (Gastrophysa) viridula caucasica Jolivet, 1951

Distribution: Caucasus

Gastrophysa (Gastrophysa) viridula lenta (J. Weise, 1887)

Distribution: Asian Russia (E Siberia, Russian Far East), Mongolia

Genus ***Phaedon*** Dahl, 1823

Subgenus ***Phaedon (Phaedon)*** Dahl, 1823

Phaedon (Phaedon) armoraciae (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: N, Central and E Europe, Mountains of S Kazakhstan and Central Asia (except for the Turkmenistan), Asian Russia (Siberia east to Yakutia)

Phaedon (Phaedon) bogdanovikatjkovi Jacobson, 1921

Distribution: W Kazakhstan (River Emba)

Phaedon (Phaedon) cochleariae cochleariae (Fabricius, 1702)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Altai, Sayan)

Phaedon (Phaedon) cochleariae brassicae (Baly, 1874)

Distribution: Russian Far East, Korea, China, Japan

Phaedon (Phaedon) concinnus Stephens, 1834

Distribution: N, NW and E Europe (Baltic States, N European Russia), Asian Russia (N Siberia and Russian Far East), Mongolia

Phaedon (Phaedon) laevigatus (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: S and Central Europe, Ukraine, S European Russia, Caucasus

Subgenus ***Phaedon (Hemiphaedon)*** Jacobson, 1901

Phaedon (Hemiphaedon) magnificus Lopatin, 1985

Distribution: Kazakhstan (Barsakeljmes Isle in Aral Sea)

Phaedon (Hemiphaedon) subtilis subtilis J. Weise, 1900
Distribution: Plains of Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan

Phaedon (Hemiphaedon) subtilis opacus Lopatin, 1976
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan

Genus *Neophaedon* Jacobson, 1901

Neophaedon pyritosus alutaceus Fleischer, 1909
Distribution: W Kazakhstan, W Central Asia, E Iran, Afghanistan

Neophaedon pyritosus pyritosus (Rossi, 1792)
Distribution: S and E Europe, Caucasus, N Kazakhstan, N Africa

Genus *Sternoplatys* Motschulsky, 1860

Subgenus *Sternoplatys (Sternoplatys)* Motschulsky, 1860

Sternoplatys (Sternoplatys) clementzi Jacobson, 1901
Distribution: S Asian Russia (S Siberia, Altais, Tuva, Yakutia)

Sternoplatys (Sternoplatys) fausti J. Weise, 1884
Distribution: SE and E Asian Russia (Magadan Distr. Ussuri Area)

Sternoplatys (Sternoplatys) fulvipes fulvipes Motschulsky, 1860
Distribution: Asian Russia (E Amurland, Maritime Prov.), NE China

Sternoplatys (Sternoplatys) fulvipes baicalicus (J. Weise, 1900)
Distribution: S Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, W Amurland)

Sternoplatys (Sternoplatys) segnis J. Weise, 1884
Distribution: Mountains of Central and SE Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians

Subgenus *Sternoplatys (Austrosteronoplatys)* Jacobson, 1921

Sternoplatys (Austrosteronoplatys) longulus J. Weise, 1890
Distribution: High Mountains Ranges of S Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan

Genus *Sclerophaedon* J. Weise, 1882

Sclerophaedon carniolicus (Germar, 1824)
Distribution: Mountains of Central and SE Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians

Sclerophaedon carpathicus (J. Weise, 1875)

Distribution: Mountains of Central Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians

Sclerophaedon orbicularis (Suffrian, 1851)

Distribution: Mountains of Central Europe, Ukrainian Carpathians

Genus ***Oreothassa*** Jacobson, 1900

Oreothassa matjanovi Jacobson, 1900

Distribution: E Kazakhstan, S Asian Russia (Altai)

Genus ***Hydrothassa*** J. Thomson, 1866

Subgenus ***Hydrothassa (Agrostithassa)*** Jacobson, 1921

Hydrothassa (Agrostithassa) glabra (Herbst, 1783)

Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North, W Siberia, NW Africa

Subgenus ***Hydrothassa (Hydrothassa)*** J. Thomson, 1886

Hydrothassa (Hydrothassa) hannoveriana (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution: Central Europe, Ukraine and European Russia except for Steppe zone, Siberia

Hydrothassa (Hydrothassa) marginella marginella (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe except for S, Kazakhstan, S Asian Russia (S Siberia east to Yakutia)

Hydrothassa (Hydrothassa) marginella eoa Lopatin, 1962

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.)

Genus ***Apterocuris*** Jacobson, 1900

Apterocuris sibirica (Gebler, 1830)

Distribution: S Asian Russia (Altai)

Genus ***Prasocuris*** Latreille, 1802

Prasocuris junci (Brahm, 1790)

Distribution: S, Central and E Europe, Caucasus, S Kazakhstan

Prasocuris phellandrii (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, N China

Genus *Plagioder*a Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

*Plagioder*a *versicolor*a (Laicharting, 1781)

Distribution: All over Holarctic, India, Taiwan

Genus *Chrysomela* Linnaeus, 1758

Subgenus *Chrysomela* (*Pachylina*) L. Medvedev in Medvedev et Chernov, 1969

Chrysomela (*Pachylina*) *blaisdelli blaisdelli* Van Dyke, 1938

Distribution: NE Asian Russia (Chukotka), Alaska, N Canada

Chrysomela (*Pachylina*) *blaisdelli taimyrensis* L. Medvedev, 1969

Distribution: N Asian Russia (Taimyr Peninsula)

Chrysomela (*Pachylina*) *blaisdelli vrangeliana* L. Medvedev, 1973

Distribution: NE Asian Russia (Wrangel Is.)

Chrysomela (*Pachylina*) *collaris* Linnaeus, 1758

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for Central Asia

Subgenus *Chrysomela* (*Macrolina*) Motschulsky, 1860

Chrysomela (*Macrolina*) *cuprea* Fabricius, 1775

Distribution: All over the Palaearctic except for Central Asia

Chrysomela (*Macrolina*) *lapponica* Linnaeus, 1758

Distribution: N, Central and E Europe, Kyrgyzstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Tuva, Yakutia, Russian Far East, Sakhalin)

Chrysomela (*Macrolina*) *vigintipunctata* (Scopoli, 1763)

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for Middle Asia

Subgenus *Chrysomela* (*Chrysomela*) Linnaeus, 1758

Chrysomela (*chrysomela*) *populi* Linnaeus, 1758

Distribution: All over Palaearctic, Mountains of S Kazakhstan and Middle Asia

Chrysomela (*chrysomela*) *saliceti* (J. Weise, 1884)

Distribution: All over the Palaearctic except for Middle Asia

Chrysomela (*chrysomela*) *tremula* Fabricius, 1787

Distribution: All over the Palaearctic except for Middle Asia

Chrysomela (chrysomela) turkestanica G. Reineck, 1937

Distribution: Mountains of Middle Asia, Afghanistan

Genus ***Linaeidea*** Motschulsky, 1860

Linaeidea aenea (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe except for extreme North, E Kazakhstan, Siberia, N China, Japan

Genus ***Gastrolina*** Baly, 1859

Gastrolina depressa Baly, 1859

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Gastrolina peltoidea (Gebler, 1832)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Central Siberia, Yakutia, Transbaikalia, Russian Far East, Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), NE China, Japan

Genus ***Gastrolinoides*** Chujo et Kimoto, 1960

Gastrolinoides japonica (Harold, 1877)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Japan

Subtribus ***Doryphorina*** Yuasa, 1936

Genus ***Leptinotarsa*** Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Leptinotarsa decemlineata (Say, 1824)

Distribution: Introduced from N America. Europe, Caucasus, European Russia east to Astrakhan Distr. and Kalmykia

Genus ***Zygogramma*** Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Zygogramma suturalis (Fabricius, 1775)

Distribution: Introduced from N America. Ciscaucasia, W Caucasus

Subtribus ***Entomoscelina*** Reitter, 1912

Genus ***Cystocnemis*** Motschulsky, 1860

Cystocnemis concolor (Kraatz, 1879)

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan (Saur and Tarbagatay Mountain Ranges)

Cystocnemis discoidea (Gebler, 1830)

Distribution: E Kazakhstan, S Asian Russia (S Altais)

Genus *Xenomela* J. Weise, 1884

Xenomela ballioni Lopatin, 1989

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan

Xenomela belousovi Lopatin, 1989

Distribution: SW Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan

Xenomela dohrni (Solsky, 1881)

Distribution: Plains of Uzbekistan and N Tajikistan

Xenomela karatavica Lopatin, 1989

Distribution: Kazakhstan (Karatau Mountain Range)

Xenomela konstantinovi Lopatin, 1995

Distribution: Uzbekistan (Chimghan Mountain Range)

Xenomela kraatzi J. Weise, 1884

Distribution: Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan (Fergan Mountain Range)

Xenomela laevigata Lopatin, 1989

Distribution: S Kyrgyzstan

Xenomela marginicollis (Ballion, 1878)

Distribution: Central and E Tian-Shan in the borders of Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan, China

Xenomela minckwitzae minckwitzae (Jacobson, 1925)

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Talas and Ugam Mountain Ranges)

Xenomela minckwitzae kreutzbergi Lopatin, 1989

Distribution: Uzbekistan (Karzantau Mountain Range)

Xenomela minckwitzae pskemica Lopatin, 1989

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Pskem Mountain Range)

Xenomela ovczinnikovi Lopatin, 1995

Distribution: Uzbekistan (Kuramin Mountain Range)

Xenomela regeli Jacobson, 1897

Distribution: Uzbekistan (Sailyk Mountain, Karzantau Mountain Range)

Subgenus *Oreomela (Olcomela)* Jacobson, 1895

Oreomela (Olcomela) korolkovi Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: E Kazakhstan (Dzhungar Alatau Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Olcomela) suvorovi Jacobson, 1910

Distribution: E. Kazakhstan (Dzhungar Alatau Mountain Range), NW China

Subgenus *Oreomela (Oreomela)* Jacobson, 1895

Oreomela (Oreomela) abramovi Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Talas Alatau Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) andreevi Jacobson, 1910

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Terskey Alatau Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) bergi Jacobson, 1910

Distribution: S Kyrgyzstan, N Tajikistan

Oreomela (Oreomela) borealis Lopatin, 1999

Distribution: Kazakhstan (Chu-Ili Mountain)

Oreomela (Oreomela) celyphoides Jacobson, 1896

Distribution: S Kazakhstan (Dzhungar Alatau Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) clypealis Jacobson, 1901

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Kyrgyzian Alatau Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) dungana Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Sarydzhaz Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) dzhungara Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: S Kazakhstan (Dzhungar Alatau Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) fuscipes (J. Weise, 1885)

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan

Oreomela (Oreomela) gracilis Lopatin, 1999

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Terskey Alatau Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) heydeni (J. Weise, 1885)

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Son-Kul Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) hohlbecki Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Kyrgyz Mountain Range)

- Oreomela (Oreomela) jacobsoni*** (Semenov, 1894)
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Alai Mountain Range)
- Oreomela (Oreomela) joliveti*** Lopatin, 1976
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan (Ketmen Mountain Range)
- Oreomela (Oreomela) juldusana*** Lopatin, 1962
Distribution: NW China
- Oreomela (Oreomela) kabaki*** Lopatin, 1995
Distribution: E Kazakhstan
- Oreomela (Oreomela) kaszabi*** Lopatin, 1962
Distribution: Tibet
- Oreomela (Oreomela) korotjaevi*** Lopatin, 1983
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan
- Oreomela (Oreomela) kungeica*** Lopatin, 1976
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Kunghey Alatau Mountain Range)
- Oreomela (Oreomela) kutzenkoi*** Jacobson, 1925
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Atbashy Mountain Range)
- Oreomela (Oreomela) lopatini*** Grujev, 1991
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Susamyr Mountain Range)
- Oreomela (Oreomela) medvedevi*** Lopatin, 1968
Distribution: E Tajikistan (Badakhshan)
- Oreomela (Oreomela) mitjaevi*** Lopatin, 1996
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan
- Oreomela (Oreomela) montivaga*** Lopatin, 1987
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Susamyr Mountain Range)
- Oreomela (Oreomela) pedaschenkoi*** Jacobson, 1925
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Terskey Alatau and Atbashy Mountain Ranges)
- Oreomela (Oreomela) puncticollis*** Lopatin, 1999
Distribution: E Kazakhstan (Dzhungar Alatau Mountain Range)
- Oreomela (Oreomela) radkewiczi*** Jacobson, 1925
Distribution: S Kazakhstan (Kendyktau Mountain Range)
- Oreomela (Oreomela) recticollis*** Lopatin 1995
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Kunghey Alatau Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) ruckbeili Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Terskey Alatau Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) sapozhnikovii Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Terskey Alatau, Ketmen, Sarydzhaz Mountain Ranges)

Oreomela (Oreomela) sarydzhasea Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Sarydzhaz Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) schnitnikovii Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Kyrgyz Alatau Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) scutellaris Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Sarydzhaz and Kunghey Alatau Mountain Ranges)

Oreomela (Oreomela) semenovi Jacobson, 1895

Distribution: S Kazakhstan (Transili Alatau Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) sussamyrica Lopatin, 1987

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Susamyr Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) tarantscha Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan

Oreomela (Oreomela) tarbagataica Lopatin, 1968

Distribution: E Kazakhstan (Tarbagatay Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) transalaica Lopatin, 1965

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Transalai Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) transiliensis Lopatin, 1976

Distribution: S Kazakhstan (Transili Alatau Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) tschernavini Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Susamyr Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) wisei Jacobson, 1895

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Terskey Alatau Mountain Range)

Oreomela (Oreomela) zaslavskii Lopatin, 1976

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Atbashy Mountain Range)

Subgenus ***Oreomela (Entomomela)*** Jacobson, 1925

Oreomela (Entomomela) arnoldii Lopatin, 1974

Distribution: E Kazakhstan (Azatau Mountain Range)

Genus *Entomoscelis* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Entomoscelis adonidis (Pallas, 1771)

Distribution: S and SE Europe, Lithuania, Ukraine, European Russia except for northern parts, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Central Asia except for Deserts of Turkmenistan, Asian Russia (Siberia, Yakutia, Russian Far East), Mongolia, N China

Entomoscelis deserticola Lopatin, 1967

Distribution: China (Sinkiang)

Entomoscelis erythrocnema Jacobson, 1893

Distribution: South parts of Central Asia, North to Nuratau Mountains in Uzbekistan

Entomoscelis orientalis Motschulsky, 1860

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, N China, Korea

Entomoscelis pilula Lopatin, 1967

Distribution: Transcaucasia

Entomoscelis sacra (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: SE Europe, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Entomoscelis suturalis J. Weise, 1882

Distribution: SE Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Middle East

Subtribus *Gonioctenina* Wilcox, 1972

Genus *Gonioctena* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Subgenus *Gonioctena (Gonioctena)* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) coreana (Bechyne, 1947)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Magadan Distr. Khabarovsk Distr., Amurland, Maritime Prov.), NE China, Korea

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) decaspilota (Achard, 1924)

Distribution: N and NE Europe, Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East), Mongolia, N China, Korea

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) decemnotata (Marsham, 1802)

Distribution: All over Holarctic except for S Europe and Central Asia

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) flavicornis flavicornis (Suffrian, 1851)

Distribution: N, Central and E Europe, Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, Japan

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) flavicornis borealis (L. Medvedev, 1963)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Kamchatka)

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) gracilicornis (Kraatz, 1879)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Siberia Russian Far East, Maritime Prov., Sakhalin), Mongolia, N China

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) honshuensis honshuensis (Nakane, 1963)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Kurile Is.), Japan

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) honshuensis ochotense (L. Medvedev, 1968)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Magadan Distr., Kamchatka)

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) honshuensis sachalinensis (L. Medvedev, 1968)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Sakhalin)

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) jacobsoni (Ogloblinet L. Medvedev, 1956)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Siberia, Magadan Distr., Maritime Prov.), Mongolia

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) janovskii L. Medvedev, 1976

Distribution: S Siberia, Mongolia

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) japonica (Chujo et Kimoto, 1960)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Kurile Is.), Japan

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) kamiyai Kimoto, 1963

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, S Maritime Prov.), Japan

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) kaufmanni (L. Miller, 1881)

Distribution: Mountains of Central and E Europe, Carpathians

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) laeta L. Medvedev, 1973

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Maritime Prov.), Korea

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) linnaeana linnaeana (Schrank, 1781)

Distribution: Europe except for Mediterranean, Caucasus, Kazakhstan except for southern parts, Asian Russia (W and S Siberia, Altai, Tuva), Mongolia

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) linnaeana bergrothi (Jacobson, 1901)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Siberia from Altai to Pacific Coast)

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) ogloblini L. Medvedev et Dubeshko, 1992

Distribution: Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) sibirica (J. Weise, 1893)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East Kamchatka, Maritime Prov.), Japan

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) sundmanni (Jacobson, 1901)

Distribution: N Europe, Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East, Kamchatka), Mongolia

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) viminalis viminalis (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: All over Holarctic except for Mediterranean, and Central Asia

Gonioctena (Gonioctena) viminalis rufa (Kraatz, 1879)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Sayan Russian Far East), Mongolia, NE China, Korea

Subgenus ***Gonioctena (Brachyphytodecta)*** Bechyne, 1947

Gonioctena (Brachyphytodecta) fulva (Motschulsky, 1860)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), E China, Vietnam

Subgenus ***Gonioctena (Goniomena)*** Motschulsky, 1860

Gonioctena (Goniomena) pallida (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: N, Central and E Europe, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Siberia, Maritime Prov.), N Mongolia

Gonioctena (Goniomena) quinquepunctata intermedia (Helliesen, 1913)

Distribution: Mountains of Central and E Europe, N and NE Europe

Gonioctena (Goniomena) quinquepunctata quinquepunctata (Fabricius, 1787)

Distribution: N, Central and E Europe, Carpathians, European Russia Asian Russia (W Siberia, Yakutia)

Subgenus ***Gonioctena (Spartophila)*** Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Gonioctena (Spartophila) olivacea (Forster, 1771)

Distribution: S and Central Europe, Belarus, Ukraine east to Kharkov, NW Africa

Subgenus ***Gonioctena (Spartoxena)*** Motschulsky, 1860

Gonioctena (Spartoxena) fornicata Bruggemann, 1873

Distribution: SE Europe, SW Ukraine, Moldavia, Turkey

Genus ***Cercyonops*** Jacobson, 1900

Cercyonops caraganae (Gebler, 1823)

Distribution: NE of European Russia, S Asian Russia (S Siberia, Altai, Tuva)

Subtribus ***Paropsina*** J. Weise, 1915

Genus ***Paropsides*** Motschulsky, 1860

Paropsides soriculatus (Swartz, 1808)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Yakutia, Transbaikalia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan, Vietnam

Subtribus ***Phratorina*** Lopatin, 1977

Genus ***Phratora*** Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Subgenus ***Phratora (Phratora)*** Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Phratora (Phratora) atrovirens (Cornelius, 1857)

Distribution: Central and E Europe, Caucasus, Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East), Mongolia

Phratora (Phratora) horioni (Mohr, 1968)

Distribution: Caucasus (Teberda)

Phratora (Phratora) laticollis (Suffrian, 1851)

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for the extreme N and Central Asia

Phratora (Phratora) polaris polaris (W. G. Schneider, 1886)

Distribution: N Europe Asian Russia (Siberia, N Russian Far East), Mongolia

Phratora (Phratora) polaris reitteri (Lopatin, 1962)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva, Cisbaikalia), Mongolia

Phratora (Phratora) tibialis (Suffrian, 1851)

Distribution: Central and E Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan

Phratora (Phratora) vitellinae (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East), Mongolia, Korea

Subgenus ***Phratora (Chaetoceroides)*** E. Strand, 1935

Phratora (Chaetoceroides) obtusicollis Motschulsky, 1860

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov., Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), Mongolia, NE China, Korea, Japan

Phratora (Chaetoceroides) vulgatissima (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe except for Mediterranean, Caucasus, E Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East), Mongolia, N America

Subfamily *Cryptocephalinae* Gyllenhal, 1813

Tribe *Cryptocephalini* Gyllenhal, 1813

Genus *Cryptocephalus* Geoffroy, 1762

Subgenus *Cryptocephalus (Protophysus)* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Cryptocephalus (Protophysus) schaefferi Schrank, 1789

Distribution: SE and southern parts of Central Europe, Caucasus, Asian Russia (S Siberia east to Transbaikalia), Kazakhstan

Subgenus *Cryptocephalus (Disopus)* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Cryptocephalus (Disopus) pini difformis (Jacoby, 1885)

Distribution: Asian Russia (E Siberia, Sakhalin), Japan

Cryptocephalus (Disopus) pini pini (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe except for the South, Asian Russia (W Siberia)

Subgenus *Cryptocephalus (Asionus)* Lopatin, 1988

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) altaicus Harold, 1872

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, Tuva, Sayan, Transbaikalia), Mongolia, China

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) apicalis Gebler, 1850

Distribution: S Ukraine (Crimea), Moldavia, Ciscaucasia, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia)

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) arnoldii arnoldii L. Medvedev, 1956

Distribution: S Kazakhstan (W Tian-Shan Mountains), Uzbekistan (Baisuntau Mountain Range), SW Tajikistan

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) arnoldii sogdianus Lopatin, 1963

Distribution: N Tajikistan (Zeravshan Mountain Range), N Uzbekistan (Nuratau Mountain Range)

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) atriplicis Lopatin, 1967

Distribution: Central and E Kazakhstan, Azerbaijan (Sumghait)

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) balassogloi Jacobson, 1895

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, N Tajikistan

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) beckeri Morawitz, 1860

Distribution: SE Russian Plain (Povolzhye), NW Kazakhstan

- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) bidentatus*** L. Medvedev, 1956
Distribution: Kazakhstan (Talas Alatau), Kyrgyzstan (W. Tian-Shan Mountain Ranges, Fergan Mountain Range), N Tajikistan (Kuramin Mountain Range)
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) bidentulus bidentulus*** Suffrian, 1854
Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva, S Transbaikalia), N and E. Mongolia
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) bidentulus klementzi*** Ogloblin, 1956
Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva), NW Mongolia
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) bidentulus subdesertus*** L. Medvedev, 1980
Distribution: S Mongolia
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) bitaeniatus*** Solsky, 1876
Distribution: Uzbekistan, S Tajikistan, Turkmenistan (Amu-Darya Valley)
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) bivulneratus*** Faldermann, 1835
Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva, Transbaikalia), Mongolia
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) bohemiensis*** Drapiez, 1819
Distribution: SE Europe, N and Central Kazakhstan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) borochoensis*** Pic, 1907
Distribution: E Kazakhstan, NW China
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) crux*** Gebler, 1848
Distribution: E Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S. Siberia, Yakutia, Tuva, Russian Far East), Mongolia
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) curda*** Jacobson, 1897
Distribution: Transcaucasia
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) diadochus*** Lopatin, 1963
Distribution: Tajikistan (Zeravshan Mountain Range)
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) dilectus*** J. Weise, 1894
Distribution: S Kazakhstan (W Tian-Shan), Kyrgyzstan, E Tajikistan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) ergenesis*** Morawitz, 1863
Distribution: NE Ciscaucasia (Ergeni), Georgia, S Urals, W and Central Kazakhstan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) fasciatointerruptus*** Berti et Rapilly, 1979
Distribution: Iran
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) flavicollis*** Fabricius, 1781
Distribution: Steppe of S Russian Plain, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) flexuosus Krynicki, 1834

Distribution: Steppe of Ukraine, Crimea, Asian Russia (SW Altai), Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) floralis Krynicki, 1834

Distribution: Crimea

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) fulmenifer Reitter, 1889

Distribution: Transcaucasia

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) gamma Herrich-Schaffer, 1829

Distribution: Steppe of S Russian Plain, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Novosibirsk Distr.)

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) globulus Lopatin, 1953

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) halophilus Gebler, 1830

Distribution: Central Kazakhstan

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) hamatus Suffrian, 1854

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Siberia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) hammadae Lopatin, 1961

Distribution: S Tajikistan

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) hauseri J. Weise, 1887

Distribution: S Kazakhstan (Kendyk Tau Mountain Range)

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) heydeni J. Weise, 1886

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan, Mountains of Central Asia to S Tajikistan (Gazimailik Mountain Range)

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) hirtipennis Fladermann, 1935

Distribution: Asian Russia (S. Siberia, Yakutia, Russian Far East), Mongolia

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) impressipygus Ogloblin, 1956

Distribution: Steppe of SE Russian Plain, Kazakhstan from Uralsk to Zaysan Lake

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) irenae Lopatin, 1958

Distribution: Tajikistan

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) iskanderi Lopatin, 1961

Distribution: Central Tajikistan

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) jaxarticus Lopatin, 1986

Distribution: W Kazakhstan

- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) karakalensis* L. Medvedev, 1955
Distribution: S Turkmenistan (Kopetdagh Mountain Range), Uzbekistan, Tajikistan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) karatavicus* Lopatin, 1971
Distribution: S Kazakhstan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) kerzhneri* Lopatin, 1968
Distribution: S Kazakhstan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) klarae* Lopatin, 1990
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) koltzei* J. Weise, 1887
Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, N China, Korea
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) korotjaevi korotjaevi* L. Medvedev, 1980
Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva) Mongolia
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) korotjaevi shamoensis* L. Medvedev, 1980
Distribution: Mongolia
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) lateralis* Suffrian, 1863
Distribution: Steppe of SE Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) lemniscatus* Suffrian, 1854
Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, N China
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) medvedevi* Lopatin, 1953
Distribution: S Turkmenistan (Kopetdagh Mountain Range), Tajikistan, NE Afghanistan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) mniczechi* Tappes, 1869
Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, Tuva, Sayan)
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) ogloblini* Lopatin, 1953
Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) oxianus* Lopatin, 1975
Distribution: S Tajikistan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) pavlovskii* Lopatin, 1956
Distribution: S Kazakhstan (W. Tian-Shan), Uzbekistan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) personatus* J. Weise, 1892
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Kyrgyz Alatau, Alai Mountain Range)
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) prasolovi* Lopatin, 1992
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan

- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) pseudolateralis* L. Medvedev, 1979
Distribution: E Kazakhstan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) quatuordecimmaculatus* D. H. Schneider, 1792
Distribution: SE Europe, Turkey
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) richteri* L. Medvedev, 1957
Distribution: Transcaucasia
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) rubi rubi* Menetries, 1832
Distribution: Transcaucasia
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) rubi glasunovi* Jacobson, 1894
Distribution: S Turkmenistan, S Kazakhstan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) rubi properus* J. Weise, 1900
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, S Tajikistan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) sarafschanensis sarafschanensis* Solsky, 1882
Distribution: Tajikistan and Kyrgyzstan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) sarafschanensis betpakdalensis* Lopatin, 1976
Distribution: Kazakhstan (Bekpakdala desert)
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) sarafschanensis duvivieri* J. Weise, 1892
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan (Syr-Darian Karatau Mountain Range)
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) sarafschanensis grumi* Lopatin, 1976
Distribution: E Kazakhstan, SW Mongolia
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) sarafschanensis iliensis* J. Weise, 1900
Distribution: Kazakhstan Folding Land (Cisaralia and Cisbalkhashia)
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) sarafschanensis narynensis* Lopatin, 1976
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Fergana Mountain Range)
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) sarafschanensis sugatensis* Lopatin, 1999
Distribution: Kazakhstan (Sjughaty Mountains)
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) sarafschanensis talassicus* Lopatin, 1976
Distribution: Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) sarafschanensis tiro* J. Weise, 1900
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Central Tian-Shan)
- Cryptocephalus (Asionus) sareptanus* Morawitz, 1863
Distribution: SE of the Russian plain, E Ciscaucasia, N, Central and E Kazakhstan

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) saryarkensis L. Medvedev et Kulenova, 1980

Distribution: Central Kazakhstan

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) spurius Lopatin, 1956

Distribution: S Turkmenistan (Kopetdagh Mountain Range)

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) stackelbergi Lopatin, 1971

Distribution: Central and E Kazakhstan

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) stschukini Faldermann, 1835

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, Tuva, Sayan, Transbaikalia, Russian Far East), Mongolia

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) tamaricis Solsky, 1867

Distribution: SE of Russian Plain, E Transcaucasia, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Mongolia, NW China

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) terminassianae Lopatin, 1967

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) undulatus Suffrian, 1854

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan (except for the Pamirs)

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) verae L. Medvedev, 1956

Distribution: W and S Turkmenistan (Kopetdagh Mountain Range)

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) volkovitschi Lopatin, 1976

Distribution: S Transcaucasia

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) zaitzevi Lopatin, 1977

Distribution: Transcaucasia

Cryptocephalus (Asionus) zinovievi L. Medvedev, 1973

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia

Subgenus *Cryptocephalus (Heterichnus)* Warchałowski, 1991

Cryptocephalus (Heterichnus) macrodactylus macrodactylus Gebler, 1830

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Altai), Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan

Cryptocephalus (Heterichnus) macrodactylus levipes Lopatin, 1999

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Central Tian-Shan)

Cryptocephalus (Heterichnus) macrodactylus persimilis Lopatin, 1956

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Kavak-Too and Susamyr Mountain Ranges)

Cryptocephalus (Heterichnus) macrodactylus prodocetus Jacobson, 1898
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Fergan and Alai Mountain Ranges)

Cryptocephalus (Heterichnus) tarsalis tarsalis J. Weise, 1887
Distribution: Mountains of Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan from Badakhshan Mountains in the east, up to Karzhantau Mountain Range in the west

Cryptocephalus (Heterichnus) tarsalis submontanus Lopatin, 1999
Distribution: S Tajikistan (Gazimailik Mountain Range)

Subgenus ***Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus)*** Geoffroy, 1762

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) alborzensis Rapilly, 1980
Distribution: E Azerbaijan, N Iran

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) anticus Suffrian, 1848
Distribution: Central and S Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Asian Russia (southern parts of W Siberia)

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) araxicola Iablokoff-Khnzorian, 1968
Distribution: S Armenia

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) aureolus aureolus Suffrian, 1847
Distribution: Europe except for the extreme North

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) aureolus transcausicus Jacobson, 1898
Distribution: Caucasus, Transcaucasia

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) bicolor Eschscholtz, 1818
Distribution: S and SE Europe, S Ukraine, Caucasus, Turkey, N Iran

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) biguttatus (Scopoli, 1763)
Distribution: Europe, E Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia)

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) biguttulatus Gebler, 1841
Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, Tuva, Sayan, E Siberia), Mongolia

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) biguttulus Suffrian, 1848
Distribution: S Crimea

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) bipunctatus bipunctatus (Linnaeus, 1758)
Distribution: Europe, Daghestan, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia)

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) bipunctatus cautus J. Weise, 1893
Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), NE China, Korea

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) bodungeni bodungeni Jacobson, 1905

Distribution: Kazakhstan (Syr-Darya River Valley), Karzhantau Mountain Range

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) bodungeni tadjhika Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: N Tajikistan, Uzbekistan (W of Fergana Valley)

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) caerulescens C. R. Sahlberg, 1839

Distribution: N and Central Europe, Asian Russia (southern parts of W Siberia, Amurland, Maritime Prov., Sakhalin)

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) coeruleans Marseul, 1875

Distribution: Asian Russia (Cisbaikalia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), N Mongolia, NE China

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) concolor Suffrian, 1847

Distribution: SE Azerbaijan (Talysh), Turkmenistan (Kopetdagh Mountains), Iran

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) cordiger (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Tuva, Altais)

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) coryli (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for the Central Asia, extreme South and North

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) cribratus Suffrian, 1847

Distribution: Caucasus, Turkey, W Turkmenistan, N Iran

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) cruciger Hellen, 1922

Distribution: N Europe

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) curtissimus Pic, 1907

Distribution: Sandy Deserts of Kazakhstan and Central Asia, delimited in the north by N beach of Aral Sea and Afghanistan in the south

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) decemmaculatus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) distinguendus D. H. Schneider, 1792

Distribution: N, Central, and western parts of East Europe, Asian Russia (Siberia, Magadan Distr.), E Kazakhstan

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) duplicatus Suffrian, 1847

Distribution: N and W Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) elongatus Germar, 1824

Distribution: Central and SE Europe, N and Central Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (southern part of W Siberia, Altais, Sayan, S Yakutia)

- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) eous*** Lopatin, 1952
Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia), Mongolia, NE China
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) flavipes*** Fabricius, 1781
Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for the Central Asia (present at Turkmenistan only), Mongolia, Korea, Japan
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) haroldi*** Kraatz, 1879
Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), NE China
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) hyacinthinus*** Suffrian, 1860
Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov., S Kurile Is.), N China, Korea, Japan
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) hypochoeridis hypochoeridis*** (Linnaeus, 1758)
Distribution: Central and E Europe, Asian Russia (Siberia), N and E Kazakhstan
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) hypochoeridis praticola*** J. Weise, 1889
Distribution: Caucasus (Abkhazia, Daghestan, Georgia)
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) hypochoeridis transiens*** Franz, 1949
Distribution: Switzerland, Yugoslavia, Slovakia, Transcarpathia
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) imperialis*** Laicharting, 1781
Distribution: Europe, S European Russia, Central Georgia, Turkey, Cyprus
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) janthinus*** Germar, 1824
Distribution: Southern parts of W and Central Europe, SE Europe, NW Caucasus, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Maritime Prov., Sakhalin)
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) kiritschenkiellus*** Lopatin, 1961
Distribution: Uzbekistan (Fergana Valley)
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) krutovskii gebleri*** Jacobson, 1924
Distribution: E Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Altai, Tuva, Cisbaikalia)
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) krutovskii krutovskii*** Jacobson, 1900
Distribution: Asian Russia (E Altai, Tuva, Cisbaikalia), Mongolia
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) krutovskii triangulifer*** Jacobson, 1926
Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, Middle Siberia, S and Middle Yakutia, Amurland, Kamchatka, Maritime Prov., Sakhalin), Japan
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) kulibini*** Gebler, 1832
Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, NE China, Korea

- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) laetus* Fabricius, 1792
Distribution: Europe except for the West and North, N Caucasus, Kazakhstan except for the South, Asian Russia (W Siberia, Altai)
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) laevicollis* Gebler, 1830
Distribution: E and SE Europe, Crimea, Ciscaucasia, Kazakhstan (except for the South), Asian Russia (southern parts of W Siberia, Altai)
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) latimargo* L. Medvedev, 1971
Distribution: Asian Russia (Cisbaikalia, Transbaikalia, Magadan Distr.), Mongolia
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) limbatipennis* Jacoby, 1885
Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), E China, Japan
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) luridipennis luridipennis* Suffrian, 1854
Distribution: Asian Russia (southern S part of W Siberia, Altai, Tuva, S Yakutia, Magadan Distr.), Mongolia, Japan
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) luridipennis pallescens* Kraatz, 1879
Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, WE China, Korea
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) mannerheimi* Gebler, 1825
Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, Tuva, S Yakutia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, N China, Korea
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) marginatus* Fabricius, 1781
Distribution: Europe except for the North
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) melanoxanthus melanoxanthus* Solsky, 1876
Distribution: Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) melanoxanthus chotanensis* (Jacobson, 1895)
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Chon-Khemin River Valley), NW China
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) melanoxanthus flaviventris* Lopatin, 1952
Distribution: Kazakhstan (Lower Ili and Kharatal Rivers), Turkmenistan
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) melanoxanthus variolosus* (Jacobson, 1894)
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Shores of Issyk-Kul Lake)
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) modestus* Suffrian, 1848
Distribution: SE of European Russia, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Altai)
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) monilis* J. Weise, 1890
Distribution: Kazakhstan, S Mongolia, N China

- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) moraei*** (Linnaeus, 1758)
Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, N Iran, Urals, Asian Russia (W Siberia, Altais)
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) multiplex liothorax*** (Solsky, 1871)
Distribution: Asian Russia (southern part of E Siberia, Maritime Prov.), N China, N Korea
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) nitidulus*** Fabricius, 1787
Distribution: N, Central and E Europe, Urals, Asian Russia (S Siberia, Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), N China, Japan
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) nitidus*** (Linnaeus, 1758)
Distribution: Europe, Asian Russia (S Siberia)
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) nobilis*** Kraatz, 1879
Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland), Japan
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) ochroloma*** Gebler, 1830
Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, Tuva, E Siberia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), N Mongolia, N China
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) octomaclatus*** Rossi, 1790
Distribution: S, Central and E Europe, Azerbaijan
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) octopunctatus*** (Scopoli, 1763)
Distribution: Europe, Ciscaucasia, W and E Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (southern parts of W Siberia, Altai)
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) orotschena*** Jacobson, 1925
Distribution: Asian Russia (northern part of W Siberia, Yakutia, Magadan Distr.)
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) oxysternus*** Jacobson, 1895
Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, NE China
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) parvulus*** O. F. Muller, 1776
Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for the Central Asia
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) peliopterus*** Solsky, 1871
Distribution: Asian Russia (S Amurland, Maritime Prov.), NE China, Japan
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) prusisus*** Suffrian, 1853
Distribution: SE Balkan Peninsula, Transcaucasia, Turkey
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) pseudocautus*** L. Medvedev, 1973
Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia)
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) punctiger*** Paykull, 1799
Distribution: N and Central Europe

- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) pustulipes*** Menetries, 1836
Distribution: Asian Russia (S. Siberia, Tuva, S Yakutia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, NE China, Korea
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) putjatae*** Jacobson, 1895
Distribution: Asian Russia (S Transbaikalia, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, NE China
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) quadriguttatus*** Richter, 1820
Distribution: Central and E Europe, Ciscaucasia, N and E Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (southern part of W. Siberia, Altai, Tuva), Mongolia
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) quadripustulatus*** Gyllenhal, 1813
Distribution: Europe, W and Middle Siberia
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) quinquepunctatus*** (Scopoli, 1763)
Distribution: Central Europe, Carpathians, Transcarpathia, Moldavia, Transcaucasia, S European Russia, S Urals
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) regalis*** Gebler, 1830
Distribution: Asian Russia (S Siberia, Altai, Tuva, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, N China, Korea, Japan
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) rufofasciatus*** Solsky, 1882
Distribution: Sandy Deserts of Kazakhstan and Central Asia from Ryn-Peski in the north up to S Uzbekistan in the south
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) ruralis*** J. Weise, 1887
Distribution: Asian Russia (S Cisbaikalia, Yakutia, Amurland, Magadan Distr.)
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) semiargenteus*** Reitter, 1894
Distribution: Deserts of S Central Asia and Kazakhstan, from lower Syr-Darya River, up to S Uzbekistan and Tajikistan
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) sericeus*** (Linnaeus, 1758)
Distribution: Europe except for the North and Mediterranean, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Turkey, N Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Siberia east to Yakutia)
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) sexpunctatus*** (Linnaeus, 1758)
Distribution: All over the Palaearctic except for the Central Asia
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) signatifrons*** Suffrian, 1847
Distribution: Europe except for the North, SE Poland, SW Ukraine (Carpathians)
- Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) splendens*** Kraatz, 1879
Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, Tuva, Sayan, Cisbaikalia, Dsauria, S Yakutia, Amurland, Maritime Prov., Sakhalin), Mongolia, NE China

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) surdus Rapilly, 1980

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) tataricus Gebler, 1841

Distribution: S and E Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Cisbaikalia, Tuva), Central Asia, SW Mongolia

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) tetredecaspilotus Baly, 1873

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Japan

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) tetratyrus Solsky, 1871

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Korea

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) tricoloratus Jacobson, 1895

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Maritime Prov.), SW China

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) trimaculatus Rossi, 1790

Distribution: S and SE Europe, Caucasus, Turkey

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) turangae Lopatin, 1961

Distribution: S Tajikistan (Vahsh and Kyzyl-Su River Valleys)

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) umbrosus Lopatin, 1956

Distribution: Iran

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) violeceus Laicharting, 1781

Distribution: Central and S Europe, Ciscaucasia

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) virens Suffrian, 1847

Distribution: Central and SE Europe, Steppe of Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia)

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) vittatus Fabricius, 1775

Distribution: W, SW and Central Europe

Cryptocephalus (Cryptocephalus) zejensis Mikhailov, 1999

Distribution: Asian Russia (Russian Far East)

Subgenus *Cryptocephalus (Burlinius)* Lopatin, 1965

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) appositus Lopatin, 1958

Distribution: S Kyrgyzstan (Fergan Mountain Range)

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) bilineatus (Linnaeus, 1767)

Distribution: Alla over the Palaeartic except for the extreme North and Central Asia

- Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) carpathicus*** Frivaldszky, 1883
Distribution: Ukrainian Carpathians, Hungary
- Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) chrysopus*** Gmelin, 1787
Distribution: Europe, N Caucasus, Asian Russia (Sayan)
- Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) confusus*** Suffrian, 1854
Distribution: Asian Russia (S Siberia, Tuva, Yakutia, Russian Far East), Mongolia
- Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) connexus*** Olivier, 1807
Distribution: Mediterranean, E Europe, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Central Asia (Steppe)
- Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) dilutellus dilutellus*** Jacobson, 1901
Distribution: Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, N and Central Tajikistan
- Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) dilutellus badakshanicus*** Lopatin, 1999
Distribution: E Tajikistan (Badakshan Mountains)
- Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) elegantulus*** Gravenhorst, 1807
Distribution: Central and SE Europe, Asian Russia (W Siberia), Turkey
- Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) exiguus*** D.H. Schneider, 1792
Distribution: Europe, Siberia
- Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) fausti*** J. Weise, 1882
Distribution: E Caucasus, (Daghestan, Azerbaijan)
- Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) fedtschenkoi*** Jacobson, 1901
Distribution: Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan
- Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) flavoscutellaris*** L. Medvedev, 1973
Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland), Korea
- Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) frontalis*** Marsham, 1802
Distribution: Europe, Asian Russia (Siberia, Maritime Prov., Sakhalin)
- Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) fulvus*** (Goeze, 1777)
Distribution: Europe, Transcaucasia, Near East, Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.) W and Central Kazakhstan, N China, Korea
- Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) gussakovskii*** Lopatin, 1952
Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.)
- Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) invisus*** Lopatin, 1963
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) kabaki Lopatin, 2002

Distribution: N China (Tzinzian)

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) kurentzovi L. Medvedev, 1966

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Kurile Is.), Japan

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) labiatus (Linnaeus, 1761)

Distribution: Europe, Asian Russia (W Siberia), Mongolia

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) lederi J. Weise, 1889

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Iran, Afghanistan, Turkmenistan (Kopetdagh Mountains)

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) macellus Suffrian, 1860

Distribution: S and Central Europe, Transcaucasia, Near and Middle East, N Africa

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) nigrofasciatus Jacoby, 1885

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov., Sakhalin), N China, Mongolia, Japan

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) ocellatus Drapiez, 1819

Distribution: Europe Except for the North, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (S Siberia)

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) ochroleucus Stephens, 1839

Distribution: Europe, Steppe zone of Ukraine, Transcaucasia, Middle East, NW Africa

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) pallifrons Gyllenhal, 1813

Distribution: Europe except for the South, Urals, Kazakhstan (except for the South), Asian Russia (W Siberia, Sayan, Yakutia, Maritime Prov.)

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) planifrons J. Weise, 1882

Distribution: Southern part of Central and East Europe, Balkans, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (southern part of W Siberia)

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) polymorphus polymorphus Solsky, 1882

Distribution: Mountain Areas of Central Asia and S Kazakhstan, north to Transili Alatau, Afghanistan

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) polymorphus parallelus Jacobson, 1895

Distribution: Tajikistan (Vakhsh and Khozratishoh Mountain Ranges)

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) polymorphus schmidtii Jacobson, 1894

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Issyk-Kul Depression)

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) populi Suffrian, 1848

Distribution: W, Central and southern E Europe, Caucasus, Transcaucasia, E Kazakhstan

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) pusillus Fabricius, 1777

Distribution: Europe except for the North, Caucasus, Turkey, Algeria

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) pygmaeus Fabricius, 1792

Distribution: W, SW, Central and southerwest parts of E Europe, N Africa

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) saliceti G. Zebe, 1855

Distribution: N Europe, northern parts and Mountains of Central and East Europe

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) shabalinae Lopatin, 1968

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) tschimganensis tschimganensis J. Weise, 1894

Distribution: SW Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, S Tajikistan

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) tschimganensis narzykulovi Lopatin, 1958

Distribution: Tajikistan

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) variceps J. Weise, 1884

Distribution: SE Balkans, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Iran

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) vittula Suffrian, 1848

Distribution: Central, S and SE Europe, Caucasus

Cryptocephalus (Burlinius) xanthus Iablokoff-Khnzorian, 1968

Distribution: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Iran

Genus ***Melixanthus*** Suffrian, 1854

Melixanthus granularis (Suffrian, 1857)

Distribution: S Transcaucasia, Turkmenistan, Jordan, Arabia

Melixanthus pumilio (Suffrian, 1854)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Cisbaikalia, Buryatia, Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), Mongolia, Tibet, Japan

Genus ***Jaxartiolus*** Jacobson, 1922

Jaxartiolus baeckmannianus Jacobson, 1922

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan (Rivers Amu-Darya and Vakhsh)

Jaxartiolus reductosignatus Lopatin, 1963

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Central Tian-Shan)

Tribe *Pachybrachini* Chapuis, 1874

Genus *Pachybrachis* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Pachybrachis abditus Lopatin, 1991

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (N Coast of Issyk-Kul Lake)

Pachybrachis absinthii Lopatin, 1990

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan

Pachybrachis albicans (J. Weise, 1882)

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey

Pachybrachis altimontanus (Lopatin, 1968)

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Fergan and Alai Mountain Ranges)

Pachybrachis amurensis L. Medvedev, 1973

Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia

Pachybrachis arnoldii (Lopatin, 1967)

Distribution: N and NW Kazakhstan, Mongolia

Pachybrachis atraphaxidis (Lopatin, 1968)

Distribution: S and SE Kazakhstan

Pachybrachis auliensis (Breit, 1921)

Distribution: S and E Kazakhstan

Pachybrachis caprea caprea (J. Weise, 1887)

Distribution: Kazakhstan and Central Asia (except for Turkmenistan)

Pachybrachis caprea dzhungaricus L. Medvedev et Rybakova, 1980

Distribution: Mongolia

Pachybrachis caraganae Lopatin, 1977

Distribution: Mongolia (Mongol Mountain Range and Ghobi Altai)

Pachybrachis carpathicus (Rey, 1883)

Distribution: Ukrainian Transcarpathia, Romania

Pachybrachis cribricollis (Pic, 1907)

Distribution: SE of European Russia, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan

Pachybrachis curtipennis (Breit, 1921)

Distribution: Uzbekistan

Pachybrachis distictopygus (Jacobson, 1901)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Siberia, Maritimie Prov.), Mongolia, NE China

Pachybrachis fimbriolatus (Suffrian, 1848)

Distribution: S, Central and SE Europe, Ukraine, S European Russia, NW Caucasus, Daghestan, Turkey

Pachybrachis fraudator Lopatin, 1991

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan (Kyrgyz Alatau)

Pachybrachis ghilarovi Lopatin, 1974

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan

Pachybrachis glycyrrhizae (Olivier, 1808)

Distribution: Transcaucasia, S Central Asia, Near and Middle East

Pachybrachis heptapotamicus Lopatin, 1997

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, E Turkmenistan

Pachybrachis hieroglyphicus (Laicharting, 1781)

Distribution: Central, E, and S Europe, S Urals, E Kazakhstan, Russian Far East

Pachybrachis hippophaes (Suffrian, 1848)

Distribution: Mountains of E and Central Europe (Alps and Carpathian)

Pachybrachis instabilis (J. Weise, 1887)

Distribution: Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan (Karatau, Karzhantau, Kendyktau Mountain Ranges)

Pachybrachis issykensis issykensis (Jacobson, 1901)

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Central and S Tian-Shan)

Pachybrachis issykensis gussakovskii (Lopatin, 1968)

Distribution: Tajikistan (Hissar Mountain Range, Darvaz)

Pachybrachis issykensis laevigatus (Breit, 1921)

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan up to Pamirs

Pachybrachis jacobsoni (Lopatin, 1968)

Distribution: Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan

Pachybrachis kaplini Lopatin, 1986

Distribution: Turkmenistan (Kara-Kum)

Pachybrachis kazachstanicus Lopatin, 1974

Distribution: NW Kazakhstan

Pachybrachis kirgizicus kirgizicus Lopatin, 1974

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (N Coast of Issyk-Kul Lake)

Pachybrachis kirgizicus salsolae Lopatin, 1974

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan, Central Tian-Shan

Pachybrachis koktumensis Lopatin, 1991

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan (Dzhungar Alatau)

Pachybrachis korotjaevi Lopatin, 1995

Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva)

Pachybrachis kuramensis Lopatin, 1974

Distribution: N Tajikistan (Kuramin Mountain Range)

Pachybrachis latipes Lopatin, 1971

Distribution: E Kazakhstan, SW Mongolia

Pachybrachis limbatus (Menetries, 1836)

Distribution: Balkans, Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near East

Pachybrachis lopatini L. Medvedev et Rybakova, 1980

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Siberia, Transbaikalia, Maritime Prov.) NE Mongolia, NE China

Pachybrachis marki Lopatin, 1997

Distribution: S Tajikistan

Pachybrachis mendax (Suffrian, 1860)

Distribution: Moldavia, S Ukraine, Crimea, Ciscaucasia, Transcaucasia, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (E Siberia, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, W China

Pachybrachis merkensis (Lopatin, 1968)

Distribution: S Kyrgyzstan, S Kazakhstan

Pachybrachis mitjaevi Lopatin et Kulenowa, 1982

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan

Pachybrachis mogol Lopatin, 1986

Distribution: S Tajikistan

Pachybrachis nigropunctatus (Suffrian, 1854)

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey, Near and Middle East, Steppe and Semi-deserts of Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Afghanistan

Pachybrachis nitidicollis (J. Weise, 1894)

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Central Asia (except for the Turkmenistan), Afghanistan

Pachybrachis ochropygus (Solsky, 1872)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, Korea, NE China

Pachybrachis paganus Lopatin, 1990

Distribution: S Kazakhstan

Pachybrachis pallidulus (Suffrian, 1851)

Distribution: SE and southern parts of Central Europe

Pachybrachis pistor (Breit, 1921)

Distribution: Kazakhstan (except for the East), Uzbekistan

Pachybrachis pubipennis Lopatin, 1977

Distribution: Armenia

Pachybrachis rufescens Lopatin, 1974

Distribution: S Kazakhstan

Pachybrachis scripticollis (Faldermann, 1837)

Distribution: Armenia, Near East and Middle East, SW Turkmenistan

Pachybrachis scriptidorsum (Marseul, 1875)

Distribution: SE Europe, N Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Siberia, Khabarovsk Prov., Magadan Distr.), Mongolia, Korea, China

Pachybrachis semidesertus Lopatin, 1994

Distribution: W Kazakhstan

Pachybrachis sericans (Suffrian, 1860)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Middle Siberia, Transbaikalia), Mongolia

Pachybrachis sinuatus (Mulsant et Rey, 1859)

Distribution: Central and SE Europe, Turkey

Pachybrachis skopini (Lopatin, 1967)

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan

Pachybrachis tekensis Lopatin, 1983

Distribution: Turkmenistan (Kopetdagh Mountain Range)

Pachybrachis tessellatus tessellatus (Olivier, 1791)

Distribution: Ukraine, Moldavia (except for the Moountains), European Russia, NW Caucasus

Pachybrachis tessellatus orientalis (J. Weise, 1894)

Distribution: Armenia, Turkey

Pachybrachis transbaicalius L. Medvedev, 1974

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia), Central and E Mongolia

Pachybrachis tuvensis tuvensis L. Medvedev, 1974

Distribution: Asian Russia (Tuva)

Pachybrachis velarum saluki Lopatin, 1995

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai)

Pachybrachis velarum Warchałowski, 1998

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey

Pachybrachis vermicularis (Suffrian, 1854)

Distribution: SE European Russia, Daghestan, NW Kazakhstan

Genus ***Acolastus*** Gerstaecker, 1855

Acolastus anthracinus (Lopatin, 1976)

Distribution: Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan (Chatkal and Talas Mountain Ranges)

Acolastus atraphaxidis (Lopatin, 1960)

Distribution: E Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, SW Tajikistan

Acolastus badakshanicus (Lopatin, 1967)

Distribution: E Tajikistan (Badakshan), Afghanistan

Acolastus baeckmanni (Jacobson, 1916)

Distribution: Deserts of Central Asia and Kazakhstan (Kyzyl-Kum, Muyn-Kum, Tau-Kum, Saryeshkotrau)

Acolastus balchaschensis (Lopatin et Kulenova, 1982)

Distribution: E Kazakhstan

Acolastus curtus (Lopatin, 1994)

Distribution: Israel

Acolastus darvazicus (Lopatin, 1975)

Distribution: E Tajikistan (Darvaz Mountain Range)

Acolastus dzhungarus (Lopatin, 1976)

Distribution: S and SE Kazakhstan

Acolastus fausti (J. Weise, 1882)

Distribution: S Armenia and Azerbaijan, S Turkmenistan, NW Iran

Acolastus georgicus (Lopatin, 1986)

Distribution: E Georgia, Azerbaijan

Acolastus gobustanus (Lopatin, 1991)

Distribution: Azerbaijan

Acolastus gurjevae gurjevae (Lopatin, 1968)

Distribution: Uzbekistan (Aktau and Nuratau Mountain Ranges)

Acolastus gurjevae unicolor (Lopatin, 2001)

Distribution: Uzbekistan (Nuratau Mountain Range)

Acolastus hauseri (J. Weise, 1887)

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan (W Tian-Shan Mountain Ranges)

Acolastus iliensis (Lopatin, 1967)

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan

Acolastus inopinatus (Lopatin, 1992)

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan

Acolastus intermedius (Lopatin, 1968)

Distribution: Central Tajikistan

Acolastus issykensis (Lopatin, 1992)

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Coast of Issyk-Kul Lake)

Acolastus ivanovi (Jacobson, 1925)

Distribution: Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan

Acolastus jacobsoni (Lopatin, 1968)

Distribution: SE Tajikistan

Acolastus karakirgiza (Jacobson, 1925)

Distribution: Uzbekistan, Tajikistan

Acolastus karatavicus (Lopatin, 1976)

Distribution: Kazakhstan (Karatau Mountain Range, Syr-Darya River)

Acolastus karateginus (Lopatin, 1992)

Distribution: Tajikistan, (Karatechin Mountain Range)

Acolastus kaszabi (Lopatin, 1976)

Distribution: Mongolia

Acolastus khnzoriani (Lopatin, 1976)

Distribution: SE Turkmenistan (Kugitang Tau Mountain Range)

- Acolastus korotjaevi* (Lopatin, 1992)
Distribution: S Tajikistan
- Acolastus kryzhanovskii* (Lopatin, 1976)
Distribution: SE Turkmenistan
- Acolastus kuramensis* (Lopatin, 1992)
Distribution: N Tajikistan (Kuramin Mountain Range)
- Acolastus limbatus* (Lopatin, 1992)
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Coast of Issyk-Kul Lake)
- Acolastus margaritae* (Lopatin, 1997)
Distribution: E Turkmenistan
- Acolastus minimus* (Jacobson, 1916)
Distribution: SE Kazakhstan, S Tajikistan
- Acolastus mogoltavicus* (Lopatin, 1992)
Distribution: N Tajikistan (Mogol Tau Mountain Range)
- Acolastus murinus* (Lopatin 1961)
Distribution: Tajikistan (Coasts of Iskander Kul Lake)
- Acolastus nanus* (Lopatin, 1976)
Distribution: SW Kazakhstan
- Acolastus nigrifrons* (Jacobson, 1916)
Distribution: Central Tajikistan (Hissar Mountain Range)
- Acolastus nuratavicus* (Lopatin, 1992)
Distribution: Uzbekistan (Nuratau Mountain Range)
- Acolastus pallidus pallidus* (Lopatin, 1956)
Distribution: Tajikistan
- Acolastus pallidus montanus* (Lopatin, 1976)
Distribution: E Tajikistan (Badakhshan)
- Acolastus pallidus tianshanicus* (Lopatin, 1999)
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan
- Acolastus postfasciatus* (Lopatin, 1975)
Distribution: S Tajikistan
- Acolastus przewalskii* (Lopatin, 1992)
Distribution: Kyrgyzstan (Coasts of Issyk-Kul Lake)

Acolastus regeli (Jacobson, 1898)

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan, NW China

Acolastus shahristanus (Lopatin, 1987)

Distribution: Uzbekistan

Acolastus similis (Lopatin, 1976)

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan, S Tajikistan

Acolastus sogdianus (Lopatin, 1992)

Distribution: S Tajikistan, S Uzbekistan, SE Turkmenistan

Acolastus spitameni (Lopatin, 1990)

Distribution: N Tajikistan (Zervashan Mountain Range)

Acolastus tadzhibajevi (Lopatin, 1975)

Distribution: Tajikistan (Gazimailik and Hissar Mountain Ranges)

Acolastus tadzhicus (Lopatin, 1968)

Distribution: S Uzbekistan, S Tajikistan

*Acolastus tatiana*e (Lopatin, 1983)

Distribution: N Tajikistan (Zervashan Mountain Range)

Acolastus transcaspicus (Pic, 1900)

Distribution: Turkmenistan

Acolastus turkestanicus (Lopatin, 1965)

Distribution: N Tajikistan

Acolastus velutinus (Lopatin, 1967)

Distribution: E Tajikistan

Acolastus volkovitschi (Lopatin, 1986)

Distribution: S Uzbekistan

Acolastus zaissanicus (Lopatin, 1967)

Distribution: E Kazakhstan

Acolastus zerafschanicus (Lopatin, 1960)

Distribution: Uzbekistan (Zeravshan Mountain Range)

Tribe *Stylosomini* Clavareau, 1913

Genus *Stylosomus* Suffrian, 1848

Subgenus *Stylosomus (Microsomus)* Burlini, 1968

Stylosomus (Microsomus) costatus Lopatin, 1962

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan

Stylosomus (Microsomus) major Breit, 1918

Distribution: Kazakhstan and Central Asia (from Kopetdagh Mountain Range in the west, up to E Kazakhstan in the east), Monogolia

Stylosomus (Microsomus) weberi Reitter, 1905

Distribution: Mountains of S Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Subgenus *Stylosomus (Microstylus)* Rey, 1883

Stylosomus (Microstylus) ater Lopatin, 1962

Distribution: Kazakhstan (Transili and Karatau Mountain Ranges), Krygyzstan and Uzbekistan (W Tian-Shan)

Stylosomus (Microstylus) cylindricus Morawitz, 1860

Distribution: S Ukraine and European Russia, Caucasus, Kazakhstan

Stylosomus (Microstylus) tadzhicus Lopatin, 1965

Distribution: Mountains of Tajikistan

Subgenus *Stylosomus (Stylosomus)* Suffrian, 1848

Stylosomus (Stylosomus) cheni Lopatin, 1962

Distribution: S and E Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan

Stylosomus (Stylosomus) submetallicus Chen, 1941

Distribution: NW China

Stylosomus (Stylosomus) tamaricis tamaricis (Herrich-Schaffer, 1838)

Distribution: S of European Russia, Ukraine, Caucasus

Stylosomus (Stylosomus) tamaricis nigrifrons Fleischer, 1909

Distribution: Kazakhstan, Central Asia

Subfamily *Galerucinae* Latreille, 1802

Tribe *Galerucini* Latreille, 1802

Genus *Clitena* Baly, 1864

Clitena fuscipennis (Jacoby, 1885)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov., S Kurile Is.), Korea, Japan

Genus *Diorhabda* J. Weise, 1883

Diorhabda elongata elongata (Brulle, 1832)

Distribution: Mediterranean, Central Asia

Diorhabda elongata carinata (Faldermann, 1837)

Distribution: E Kazakhstan, NW China

Diorhabda elongata deserticola Chen, 1961

Distribution: E Kazakhstan, NW China

Diorhabda fischeri (Faldermann, 1837)

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey, W Iran, Turkmenistan

Diorhabda nigrifrons Laboissiere, 1914

Distribution: S Armenia, N Turkey

Diorhabda persica (Faldermann, 1837)

Distribution: SE of European Russia, Daghestan, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Near and Middle East

Diorhabda rickmersi J. Weise, 1900

Distribution: Tajikistan

Diorhabda rybakovi J. Weise, 1890

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan, NW China

Diorhabda tarsalis J. Weise, 1889

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Siberia), Mongolia, NW China

Genus *Galerucella* Crotch, 1873

Subgenus *Galerucella (Galerucella)* Crotch, 1873

Galerucella (Galerucella) aquatica (Geoffroy in Fourcroy, 1785)

Distribution: Europe

Galerucella (Galerucella) grisescens (Joannis, 1866)

Distribution: NW, Central and E Europe, Asian Russia (S. Siberia), N China

Galerucella (Galerucella) nipponensis Laboissiere, 1922

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), Korea, Japan

Galerucella (Galerucella) nymphaeae (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe, Central Asia, Asian Russia (S Siberia), Mongolia, China, Japan, N America

Galerucella (Galerucella) sagittariae (Gyllenhal, 1813)

Distribution: Europe, Asian Russia (S Siberia)

Subgenus ***Galerucella (Neogalerucella)*** Chujo, 1962

Galerucella (Neogalerucella) calmariensis (Linnaeus, 1767)

Distribution: Europe except for N and SW, Caucasus, Turkey, Asian Russia (S. Siberia), Mongolia, China, Japan, N Africa, introduced into N America

Galerucella (Neogalerucella) lineola (Fabricius, 1781)

Distribution: Europe, Asian Russia (S Siberia), Mongolia, China, Japan, N Africa

Galerucella (Neogalerucella) pusilla (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: S, Central and E Europe, Turkey, Central Asia, China

Galerucella (Neogalerucella) tenella (Linnaeus, 1761)

Distribution: N, Central and E Europe, Asian Russia (S Siberia), China, introduced into N America

Genus ***Xanthogaleruca*** Laboissiere, 1934

Xanthogaleruca aenescens (Fairmaire, 1878)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), N China

Xanthogaleruca flavescens J Weise, 1887

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.)

Xanthogaleruca luteola (O.F. Muller, 1776)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Caucasus, Turkey, N Africa, Central Asia, introduced to N America

Xanthogaleruca maculicollis (Motschulsky, 1853)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Japan

Genus *Pyrrhalta* Joannis, 1866

Pyrrhalta viburni annulicornis Baly, 1874

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), N China, Japan

Pyrrhalta viburni viburni (Paukull, 1799)

Distribution: Europe except for N and S, Caucasus, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W. Siberia), N Africa, introduced into N America

Genus *Tricholochmaea* Laboissiere, 1932

Tricholochmaea semifulva (Jacoby, 1885)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai, Sayan, Russian Far East)

Genus *Lochmaea* J. Weise, 1883

Lochmaea capreae capreae (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe, Transcaucasia, Turkey, N Kazakhstan

Lochmaea capreae cribrata Solsky, 1872

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, S Yakutia, Russian Far East), Mongolia, China, Korea

Lochmaea crataegi (Forster, 1771)

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except ofr extreme North

Lochmaea suturalis (C. G. Thomson, 1866)

Distribution: Europe except for N and S

Genus *Galeruca* Geoffroy, 1762

Subgenus *Galeruca (Galeruca)* Geoffroy, 1762

Galeruca (Galeruca) circassica Reitter, 1903

Distribution: N Caucasus, Abkhasia

Galeruca (Galeruca) dahli dahli (Joannis, 1866)

Distribution: S and Central Europe, Moldavia, S Ukraine, Crimea, Asian Russia (W Siberia, Altai, Cisbaikalia)

Galeruca (Galeruca) dahli vicina Solsky, 1872

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Russian Far East), Mongolia

Galeruca (Galeruca) daurica (Joannis, 1866)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Sayan, Cisbaikalia, Transbaikalia, Yakutia, Russian Far East), Mongolia

Galeruca (Galeruca) extensa (Motschulsky, 1861)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Maritime Prov.), China, Korea

Galeruca (Galeruca) heydeni J. Weise, 1887

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea

Galeruca (Galeruca) hyrcana L. Medvedev, 1969

Distribution: Azerbaijan

Galeruca (Galeruca) interrupta interrupta (Illiger, 1802)

Distribution: Europe except for N, Turkey, Syria, N Africa

Galeruca (Galeruca) interrupta armeniaca J. Weise, 1886

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan

Galeruca (Galeruca) interrupta circumdata (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: S, SE and Central Europe, Asian Russia (S Siberia), Mongolia

Galeruca (Galeruca) interrupta fulvimargo Reitter, 1908

Distribution: Mountains of S Kazakhstan, E Central Asia, NW China, Korea

Galeruca (Galeruca) laticollis C. R. Sahlberg, 1838

Distribution: N Europe, Mountains of Central and E Europe, NE Kazakhstan, Siberia, Mongolia

Galeruca (Galeruca) pomonae petschenega Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: SE European Russia (S Cisvolga), E Daghestan

Galeruca (Galeruca) pomonae pomonae (Scopoli, 1763)

Distribution: Europe, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (W Siberia Yakutia, Altai), Mongolia

Galeruca (Galeruca) reichardti Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), China, Korea

Galeruca (Galeruca) spectabilis spectabilis Faldermann, 1837

Distribution: Transcaucasia, N Iran

Galeruca (Galeruca) spectabilis lacericollis Semenov, 1909

Distribution: E Azerbaijan, N Iran, S Turkmenistan

Galeruca (Galeruca) spectabilis orientalis Osculati, 1844

Distribution: Turkey, Syria, W Iran, Transcaucasia

Galeruca (Galeruca) tanaceti tanaceti (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Turkey, Kazakhstan, Central Asia, Asian Russia (W Siberia, Altais)

Galeruca (Galeruca) tanaceti convexa Jacobson, 1925

Distribution: Mountains of Ciscaucasia, Armenia

Galeruca (Galeruca) tanaceti incisicollis (Motschulsky, 1860)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Siberia, Russian Far East), Mongolia

Galeruca (Galeruca) weisei Reitter, 1903

Distribution: SE Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Siberia, Altais, Russian Far East), Mongolia

Subgenus ***Galeruca (Haptoscelis)*** J. Weise, 1886

Galeruca (Haptoscelis) melanocephala melanocephala (Ponza, 1805)

Distribution: S and Central Europe, Belarus, Ukraine, S European Russia, Ciscaucasia, W Siberia

Subgenus ***Galeruca (Emarhopa)*** J. Weise, 1886

Galeruca (Emarhopa) rufa Germar, 1824

Distribution: S and SE Europe, Ukraine, Crimea, S European Russia, Turkey

Genus ***Theone*** Gistel, 1857

Theone costipennis (Kirsch, 1880)

Distribution: W Daghestan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan

Theone margelanica (Kraatz, 1882)

Distribution: Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan (Fergana Valley)

Theone octocostata octocostata (J. Weise, 1912)

Distribution: Pamirs, N India, Pakistan

Theone octocostata lopatini Mandl, 1970

Distribution: E Tajikistan (Badakhshan)

Theone silphoides silphoides (Dalman 1823)

Distribution: SE European Russia, Daghestan, Steppe of Kazakhstan

Theone silphoides artemisiae (Jacobson, 1895)

Distribution: Tajikistan

Theone silphoides kuldshensis Mandl, 1968

Distribution: E Kazakhstan, NW China

Theone silphoides scrobiculata Mandl, 1968

Distribution: E Kazakhstan (Tarbagatay Mountain Range)

Genus ***Pallasiola*** Jacobson, 1925

Pallasiola absinthii (Pallas, 1773)

Distribution: N. Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Pamirs, Asian Russia (S Siberia), N Mongolia, N China

Genus ***Nyctiphantus*** Semenov, 1902

Nyctiphantus bergi Semenov, 1904

Distribution: Kazakhstan (Shores of Balkhash Lake)

Nyctiphantus custos Semenov, 1902

Distribution: S Kazakhstan

Nyctiphantus hirtus hirtus (J. Weise, 1885)

Distribution: S and E Kazakhstan, NW China

Nyctiphantus hirtus nocturnus (Semenov, 1891)

Distribution: Turkmenistan (Karakum Desert)

Genus ***Apophylia*** J. Thomson, 1858

Apophylia eoa Ogloblin, 1936

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), Korea

Apophylia thalassina (Faldermann, 1835)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Amurland), Mongolia, China

Tribe ***Sermylassini*** Mroczkowski, 1991

Genus ***Sermylassa*** Reitter, 1912

Sermylassa halensis (Linnaeus, 1767)

Distribution: Central and E Europe, Balkans, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (Urals, W and Middle Siberia, Altai)

Tribe *Agelasticini* Chapuis, 1875

Genus *Agelasa* Motschulsky, 1860

Agelasa nigriceps Motschulsky, 1860

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), N China, Japan

Genus *Gallerucida* Motschulsky, 1860

Gallerucida bifasciata Motschulsky, 1860

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Gallerucida flavipennis Solsky, 1872

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), E China

Gallerucida gloriosa (Baly, 1861)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), N and Central China

Genus *Agelastica* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Agelastica alni alni (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for Central Asia, Introduced to N America

Agelastica alni orientalis Baly, 1878

Distribution: Central Asia, SE Kazakhstan, Mongolia, W China

Agelastica coerulea Baly, 1874

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), N. China, Korea, Japan, N America

Genus *Morphosphaera* Baly, 1861

Morphosphaera japonica (Hornstedt, 1788)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Amurland), China, Japan, India

Tribe *Luperini* Leng, 1920

Subtribus *Aucacophorina* Chapuis, 1875

Genus *Aulacophora* Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Aulacophora foveicollis (H. Lucas, 1849)

Distribution: S Europe (Mediterranean), Near and Middle East, Turkey, Transcaucasia, India, Burma, Sri Lanka

Aulacophora nigripennis Motschulsky, 1857

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Subtribus ***Luperina*** Wilcox, 1965

Genus ***Medythia*** Jacoby, 1887

Medythia suturalis nigrobilineatus (Motschulsky, 1860)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea, Japan

Medythia suturali suturalis (Motschulsky, 1860)

Distribution: S Asia

Genus ***Tschitscherinula*** Jacobson, 1908

Tschitscherinula paradoxocara Jacobson, 1908

Distribution: Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, S Tajikistan

Genus ***Stenoluperus*** Ogloblin, 1936

Stenoluperus cyaneus (Baly, 1874)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Kurile Is.), Japan

Stenoluperus nipponensis (Laboissiere, 1913)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov., Sakhalin, S Kurile Is.), China, Korea, Japan

Genus ***Nymphius*** J. Weise, 1900

Nymphius ogloblini (Bogatchev, 1947)

Distribution: Armenia, N Turkey

Nymphius pravei (Jacobson, 1899)

Distribution: S Ukraine, SE of European Russia, NW Kazakhstan

Nymphius stylifer (J. Weise, 1899)

Distribution: Georgia, Armenia

Genus ***Phyllobrotica*** Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Phyllobrotica adusta (Creutzer, 1799)

Distribution: Central and SE Europe

Phyllobrotica elegans Kraatz, 1866

Distribution: Ciscaucasia, S of Steppe Zone of Ukraine and European Russia, Crimea, Transcaucasia, Turkey

Phyllobrotica quadrimaculata (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe except for Mediterranean, Ciscaucasia, S Siberia, E Kazakhstan

Phyllobrotica signata (Mannerheim, 1825)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Siberia, Altai, Sayan, Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, N and W China

Genus ***Euliroetis*** Ogloblin, 1936

Euliroetis obscuripes Ogloblin, 1936

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Amurland, Maritime Prov.)

Euliroetis ornata (Baly, 1874)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Maritime Prov.), Korea, China, Japan

Genus ***Exosoma*** Jacoby, 1903

Exosoma collare (Hummel, 1825)

Distribution: Ukraine, S and E of European Russia, Caucasus, Syria, N Kazakhstan, SW Siberia

Exosoma flavipes (Heyden, 1878)

Distribution: Armenia, Turkey

Genus ***Euluperus*** J. Weise, 1886

Euluperus xnathopus xanthopus (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: Southern Steppe of Ukraine and European Russia, NW Kazakhstan, W Transcaucasia

Euluperus xanthopus virescens J. Weise, 1886

Distribution: E Transcaucasia

Genus ***Falsoexosoma*** Pic, 1926

Falsoexosoma cyanipennis (Reitter, 1902)

Distribution: Azerbaijan, Turkmenistan (Kopetdagh), Iran

Genus *Calomicrus* Stephens, 1832

Calomicrus altaicus altaicus (Mannerheim, 1825)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S and Middle Siberia, Russian Far East, Amurland), N Mongolia

Calomicrus altaicus eous Ogloblin, 1936

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.)

Calomicrus angorensis Pic, 1913

Distribution: Transcaucasia, Turkey

Calomicrus circumfusus (Marsham, 1802)

Distribution: Europe, W Ukraine, Belarus, W of European Russia, Moldavia, N Africa (Tunisia)

Calomicrus darvasicus Lopatin, 1975

Distribution: E Tajikistan

Calomicrus deserticola Ogloblin, 1936

Distribution: Turkmenistan

Calomicrus ghilarovi Lopatin, 1988

Distribution: S Tajikistan (Babatagh Mountain Range)

Calomicrus grandis (Jacobson, 1894)

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan, SE Kazakhstan

Calomicrus gussakovskyi Ogloblin, 1936

Distribution: S Tajikistan

Calomicrus hissaricus Ogloblin, 1936

Distribution: Central Tajikistan

Calomicrus minutus Joannis, 1866

Distribution: Asian Russia (Southern E Siberia, Khabarovsk Distr., Maritime Prov.)

Calomicrus nairicus Lopatin, 1990

Distribution: Armenia

Calomicrus palii Lopatin, 1965

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan

Calomicrus pinicola (Duftschmidt, 1825)

Distribution: Europe, W Ukraine, Northern and Central parts of European Russia

Calomicrus populi Lopatin, 1963

Distribution: Central and SE Tajikistan

Calomicrus sericeus (Jacobson, 1894)

Distribution: S Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan (Tian-Shan)

Calomicrus sugonjaevi Lopatin, 1983

Distribution: Turkmenistan (Kopetdagh)

Genus *Luperus* Geoffroy, 1762

Luperus anthracinus Ogloblin, 1936

Distribution: S Asian Russia (Altai), Mongolia

Luperus armeniacus Kiesenwetter, 1878

Distribution: Bulgaria, S Crimea, Transcaucasia

Luperus caucasicus J. Weise, 1879

Distribution: Caucasus

Luperus cyanipennis Kuster, 1848

Distribution: S and SW Ukraine, Crimea, Moldavia, Balkans

Luperus discolor Faldermann, 1837

Distribution: Transcaucasia

Luperus ehneri Jacobson, 1901

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan, SE Kazakhstan

Luperus flavilabris Ogloblin, 1941

Distribution: Tajikistan

Luperus flavipes flavipes (Linnaeus, 1767)

Distribution: All over Palaearctic except for Central Asia

Luperus flavipes obscuricorinis Ogloblin, 1936

Distribution: E Asian Russia (Russian Far East)

Luperus floralis Faldermann, 1837

Distribution: Azerbaijan

Luperus kiesenwetteri Joannis, 1866

Distribution: SE of European Russia (Steppe zone), N Kazakhstan, Transcaucasia

Luperus kiritschenkoi Ogloblin, 1936

Distribution: Crimea

Luperus longicornis longicornis (Fabricius, 1781)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asian Russia (Russian Far East)

Luperus longicornis tenebricosus Ogloblin, 1936

Distribution: Asian Russia (Yakutia)

Luperus lyperus (Sulzer, 1776)

Distribution: Central and E Europe, Asian Russia (W Siberia), Mongolia

Luperus margaritae Lopatin, 1990

Distribution: Armenia

Luperus orientalis Faldermann, 1837

Distribution: Daghestan, Transcaucasia, W Turkmenistan (Kopetdagh)

Luperus perlucidus Khnzorian, 1956

Distribution: Armenia

Luperus semiflavus Ogloblin, 1936

Distribution: NE China

Luperus similis Iablokoff-Khnzorian, 1970

Distribution: Asian Russia (Altai)

Luperus turkestanicus J. Weise, 1892

Distribution: Kyrgyzstan

Luperus viridipennis viridipennis Germar, 1824

Distribution: Mountains of Europe, W Ukraine (Carpathians), Forest and Forest-Steppe zone of European Russia

Luperus viridipennis laricis (Motschulsky, 1859)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Middle Siberia, Amurland), Mongolia, Japan

Luperus xanthopoda (Schrank, 1781)

Distribution: Southern parts of Central and E Europe, Ciscaucasia, Kyrgyzstan, SE Kazakhstan

Genus ***Atrachya*** Dejean, 1837

Atrachya menetriesi (Feldermaun, 1835)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov., Sakhalin, S Kurile Is), Korea, China, Japan

Genus ***Monolepta*** Chevrolat in Dejean, 1837

Monolepta dichroa dichroa Harold, 1877

Distribution: Asian Russia (Sakhalin), Japan

Monolepta dichroa kurilensis L. Medvedev, 1966

Distribution: Asian Russia (Kunashir Isle)

Monolepta eoa Ogloblin, 1936

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.)

Monolepta hieroglyphica biarcuata J. Weise, 1889

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), Korea, China, Japan

Monolepta nebulosa Ogloblin, 1936

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.)

Monolepta pallidula (Baly, 1874)

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Maritime Prov.), China, Japan

Monolepta quadriguttata (Motschulsky, 1860)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Mongolia, Korea, China, Japan

Monolepta russica (Gmelin, 1790)

Distribution: E Ciscaucasia, Kazakhstan, Plains of Central Asia

Monolepta semenovi Ogloblin, 1936

Distribution: Asian Russia (S Maritime Prov.), China

Monolepta subseriata J. Weise, 1887

Distribution: Asian Russia (Transbaikalia, Amurland, Maritime Prov.)

Genus ***Fleutiauxia*** Laboissiere, 1933

Fleutiauxia armata (Baly, 1874)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), Korea, China, Japan

Subfamily ***Lamprosomatinae*** Gemminger et Harold, 1874

Tribe ***Lamprosomatini*** Gemminger et Harold, 1874

Genus ***Oomorphus*** Curtis, 1831

Oomorphus concolor (Sturm, 1807)

Distribution: Central, SE and S Europe, Caucasus

Oomorphus nigrocoeruleus (Baly, 1873)

Distribution: Asian Russia (Maritime Prov.), China, Japan

Subfamily ***Orsodacninae*** J. Thomson, 1866

Genus ***Orsodacne*** Latreille, 1802

Orsodacne cerasi (Linnaeus, 1758)

Distribution: Europe, Caucasus, Asian Russia (W Siberia, Altai, Cisbaikalia)

Orsodacne lineola (Panzer, 1795)

Distribution: Europe except for the North, Mediterranean

Subfamily ***Megalopodinae*** Clavareau, 1913

Genus ***Temnaspis*** Lacordaire, 1845

Temnaspis bonneuili Pic, 1947

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.)

Genus ***Clythraeloma*** Kraatz, 1879

Clythraeloma cyanipennis Kraatz, 1879

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.), China, Korea

Subfamily ***Synetinae*** Edwards, 1953

Genus ***Syneta*** Lacordaire, 1845

Syneta adamsi Baly, 1877

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Khabarovsk Prov., Maritime Prov., Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), China, Korea

Syneta betulae betulae (Fabricius, 1792)

Distribution: N and northern parts of E Europe, Asian Russia (Siberia east to Transbaikalia), Mongolia

Syneta betulae amurensis Pic, 1901

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Khabarovsk Prov., Maritime Prov., Sakhalin)

Subfamily *Zeugophorinae* Chujo, 1952

Genus *Zeugophora* Kunze, 1818

Subgenus *Zeugophora (Zeugophora)* Kunze, 1818

Zeugophora (Zeugophora) bimaculata Kraatz, 1879

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov.)

Zeugophora (Zeugophora) flavicollis (Marsham, 1802)

Distribution: N, Central and E Europe, Kazakhstan, Asian Russia (W. Siberia, Tuva, Yakutia)

Zeugophora (Zeugophora) frontalis Suffrian, 1841

Distribution: Europe, Asian Russia (Siberia, Tuva, Sakhalin)

Zeugophora (Zeugophora) hozumii Chujo, 1953

Distribution: Russian Far East, Japan

Zeugophora (Zeugophora) scutellaris Suffrian, 1841

Distribution: Central and E Europe, Ciscaucasia, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Asian Russia (southern W. Siberia, Altai)

Zeugophora (Zeugophora) subspinosa (Fabricius, 1781)

Distribution: All over the Palearctic except for the Central Asia

Zeugophora (Zeugophora) turneri Power, 1863

Distribution: Central and East Europe, Asian Russia (southern W. Siberia, Transbaikalia), Mongolia

Zeugophora (Zeugophora) wisei Reitter, 1889

Distribution: Armenia, N Iran

Subgenus *Zeugophora (Pedrillia)* Westwood, 1864

Zeugophora (Pedrillia) annulata Baly, 1873

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Khabarovsk Prov., Maritime Prov., Sakhalin, Kurile Is.), China, Korea, Japan

Zeugophora (Pedrillia) bicolor Kraatz, 1879

Distribution: Asian Russia (Amurland, Maritime Prov., Kurile Is.), China

References

- [1] Askevold. I. S. 1990, Reconstructed phylogeny and reclassification of the genera Donaciinae (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae), *Quaestiones Entomologicae*, 26: 601-664
- [2] Bienkowski A. O. 1997, New distributional records for several palaeartic Chrysomelidae species with some systematic remarks (Insecta: Coleoptera), *Faunistische Abhandlungen*, 21(4): 91-104
- [3] Bienkowski A. O. 1997, Some surprising discoveries of *Chrysolina relucens* (Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae) on the White Sea shore, in Siberia and in the Far East, *Entomologica Fennica*, 7: 195-199
- [4] Bienkowski A. O. 1998, Morphology and systematics of larvae of some *Chrysolina* species (Insecta: Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae), *Entomologische Abhandlungen*, 58(4): 73-82
- [5] Bienkowski A. O. 1998, Revision of the subgenus *Anopachys* Motschulsky, 1860 of the genus *Chrysolina* Motschulsky, 1869 (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Chrysomelinae), *Genus*, 9(2): 95-153
- [6] Biondi M. 1995, The *Longitarsus anchusae* complex in Near Eastern and description of a new species (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Alticinae), *Nouvelle Revue d'Entomologie*, 12(4): 259-271
- [7] Borowiec L. Świętojańska J. 2001, The Palearctic species of the genus *Rhytidocassis* Spaeth, 1941 (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Cassidinae), *Annale Zoologici*, 51: 325-329
- [8] Doberl M. 1994, Eine neue Alticine von Kaspischen Meer: *Batophila dogueti* nov. spec. (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Alticinae), *Nouvelle Revue d'Entomologie*, 11(2): 149-150
- [9] Gruev B. 1991, *Oreomela lopatini*- a new species of *Oreomela* Jacobson (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Chrysomelinae) form the USSR (Kyrghyz SRR), *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica*, 41: 67-68
- [10] Gruev B. 1994, New distributional data about some leaf beetles in the Korean Peninsula, and descriptions of four new species (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae), *Insecta Koreana*, 11: 75-84
- [11] Kimoto S. 1993, New or little known Chrysomelidae (Coleoptera) from Japan and its adjacent regions, VI, *Entomological Review of Japan*, 48(1): 93-101
- [12] Konstantinov A. S. 1991, On taxonomy of *Asiorestia* Jacobson (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Alticinae), *Entomological Review Scripta Technica Inc*, 1991: 143-144
- [13] Konstantinov A.S. 1992, Four new species of *Longitarsus* from west Tien Shan (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Alticinae), *Elytron*, 6: 41-46
- [14] Konstantinov A. S. 1996, Review of the Palearctic species of *Crepidodera* (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Alticinae), *Spixiana*, 19(1): 21-37
- [15] Konstantinov A. S., Lopatin I. K. 1992, On the taxonomy of *Phyllotreta* Chev. of the Palearctic region(Coleoptera. Chrysomelidae: Alticinae). *Spixiana* 15(3): 261-267

- [16] Konstantinov A. S., Lopatin I. K. 2000, Review of the *Longitarsus asperifoliarum* group of species (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Alticinae), *The Coleopterists Bulletin*, 54(2): 200-220
- [17] Lopatin I. K. 1992, Zwei neue Chrysolina Arten aus Süd-Osteichen Kazakhstan (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae), *Elytron*, 6: 5-9
- [18] Mikhailov Y. E. 1999, A new species of the genus *Cryptocephalus* Geoffr. (Coleoptera. Chrysomelidae) from the Russian Far East, *Russian Entomological Journal* 8(2): 129-130
- [19] Mikhailov Y. E. 2000, New and little know leaf beetles of the genus *Chrysolina* Motsch. Form Altai and Sayan Mts. in South Siberia (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae), *Genus*, 11(2): 129-146
- [20] Mikhailov Y. E. 2002, Contribution to the knowledge of the subgenus *Chrysolina* (Pezocrosita) Jacobson, 1901 three new species from Tuva and the Urals (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae), *Nouvelle Revue d'Entomologie*, 19(1): 57-71
- [21] Mikhailov Y. E., Hayashi M. 2002, Chrysomelidae of Sakhalin II, *Entomological Review of Japan*, 57(1): 29-46
- [22] Warchałowski A. 1991, Eine nomenklatorische Änderung innerhalb der Gattung *Chrysolina* Motschulsky, *Genus*, 2(3): 281-282
- [23] Warchałowski A. 1991, Kurze Übersicht der oberseits hellen *Calomicrus* Steph. Arten (Chrysomelidae: Galerucinae), *Genus* 2(1): 41-55
- [24] Warchałowski A. 1991, Über die rot und Schwarz gefleckten Arten der Untergattung *Captocephala* (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Clytrinae), *Genus* 2(3): 229-279
- [25] Warchałowski A. 1998, Über einige kleinasiatische Arten der Gattung *Pachybrachis* Chevrolat, 1837 (Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae: Cryptocephalinae), *Annales Zoologici*, 48(1/2): 85-90
- [26] Warchałowski A. 1999, Übersicht der westpalaarktischen Arten der Untergattung *Burlinius* Lopatin, 1965 (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Cryptocephalus), *Genus*, 10(4): 529-627
- [27] Warchałowski A. 2000, A few nomenclatorial changes in Chrysomelidae (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae), *Genus* 11(4): 587-588
- [28] Warchałowski A. 2000, A short review of the genus *Chilotomina* Reitter, 1912 (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Clytrinae), *Genus* 11(4): 573-583
- [29] Igor K. Lopatin, Oleg R. Aleksandrovich, Alexander S. Konstantinov (2004). Check List of Leaf-Beetles (Coleoptera, Chrysomelidae) of the Eastern Europe and Northern Asia. The Publishing House Mantis, Olsztyn, Poland.